

N-th index D dimensional Einstein gravitational field equations

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Abstract. Aim: The possibility of the geometrization of the 2-index, 4-index and the n-th index Einstein field equations under conditions of D space-time dimensions has been investigated.

Methods: The usual tensor calculus rules were used. New rules of tensor calculus were developed too.

Results: The stress-energy-tensor $\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}$ has been geometrized under conditions of D dimensions. The Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ has been expressed completely in terms of the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ under conditions of D dimensions too. Based on the geometrized Einstein field equations under conditions of D dimensions, a procedure how to calculate the value of the cosmological constant Λ depending on the space-time dimensions D has been developed.

Conclusion: The Einstein field equations under conditions of D dimensions open the door to a logically consistent unified field theory.

1. Introduction

In point of fact, Einstein's geometrization of gravity [see 42], the gravitational field [see 17, 10] and the various proposals for a unified field theory [see 55, 18], “**a generalization of the theory of the gravitational field**” [see 24], were not yet able to produce the desired scientific success. In particular, the stress-energy momentum tensor of the electromagnetic field and Einstein's stress-energy momentum tensor of matter of the general [see 22, 17, 23, 21] theory of relativity (GTR) are the weak spots of this theory because these fields are thus far devoid [see 29] of any geometrical significance. However, in order to complete the geometrization of the general theory of relativity [see 20] as started but not completed by Einstein himself, it is necessary to geometrize the electromagnetic field and the stress energy tensor of matter too. It is necessary to expressly clarify that the dominance of geometry in physics, of the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ and today's understanding of the gravitational field as something like the manifestation of space - time curvature has closed our scientific horizon a little bit and prevents us to much from the possibility of handing over to future (scientific) generations the description of the gravitational field [see 10] by other mathematical tools [see 12, 11] than geometry. Generally speaking, although both, ‘geometrization’ and ‘unification’ are not incompatible as such, both need not to be (mathematically) conceptually identical either. The deep hope and believe that a complete geometrization of the Einstein's gravitational field equations even if a delicate and fragile plant might end up at **a unified field theory** in the sense of Einstein or Weyl's and Eddington's classical field theory in which all fundamental interactions are described by objects of space-time geometry might comfort and console our tortured scientific soul.

2. Material and methods

The first confrontation between GTR and experiment occurred on May 29, 1919 by a momentous expedition at Sobral in northern Brazil (lead by Crommelin), and on the island of Príncipe off the coast of West Africa (lead by Eddington). Astronomical observations made by this special

British team (Crommelin and Eddington) during the total solar eclipse occurred on May 29, 1919 provided the first empirical test of the validity of Einstein's general theory of relativity as discussed by the Royal Society of London and the Royal Astronomical Society announced at their joint meeting on the sixth of November 1919 [see 52, 15]. A deeper knowledge of the foundations of nature and physics as such has potential to reduce and diminish our shadows of doubts lengthened by time [11].

2.1. Definitions

Definition 2.1 (Anti tensor). Let $a_{\mu\nu}$ denote a co-variant (lower index) second-rank tensor. Let $b_{\mu\nu}$ denote another co-variant second-rank et cetera. Let $E_{\mu\nu}$ denote the sum of these co-variant second-rank tensors. Let the relationship $a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + \dots \equiv E_{\mu\nu}$ be given. A co-variant second-rank anti tensor [8] of a tensor $a_{\mu\nu}$ denoted in general as $\underline{a}_{\mu\nu}$ is defined

$$\begin{aligned}\underline{a}_{\mu\nu} &\equiv E_{\mu\nu} - a_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv b_{\mu\nu} + \dots\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

Let $a^{\mu\nu}$ denote a contra-variant (upper index) second-rank tensor. Let $b^{\mu\nu}$ denote another contra-variant (upper index) second-rank et cetera. Let $E^{\mu\nu}$ denote the sum of these contra-variant (upper index) second-rank tensors. Let the relationship $a^{\mu\nu} + b^{\mu\nu} + \dots \equiv E^{\mu\nu}$ be given. A co-variant second-rank anti tensor of a tensor $a^{\mu\nu}$ denoted in general as $\underline{a}^{\mu\nu}$ is defined

$$\begin{aligned}\underline{a}^{\mu\nu} &\equiv E^{\mu\nu} - a^{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv b^{\mu\nu} + \dots\end{aligned}\tag{2}$$

Let $a_{\mu}{}^{\nu}$ denote a mixed second-rank tensor. Let $b_{\mu}{}^{\nu}$ denote another mixed second-rank et cetera. Let $E_{\mu}{}^{\nu}$ denote the sum of these mixed second-rank tensors. Let the relationship $a_{\mu}{}^{\nu} +$

$b_\mu{}^\nu + \dots \equiv E_\mu{}^\nu$ be given. A mixed second-rank anti tensor of a tensor $a_\mu{}^\nu$ denoted in general as $\underline{a}_\mu{}^\nu$ is defined

$$\begin{aligned}\underline{a}_\mu{}^\nu &\equiv E_\mu{}^\nu - a_\mu{}^\nu \\ &\equiv b_\mu{}^\nu + \dots\end{aligned}\tag{3}$$

Symmetric tensors of rank 2 may represent many physical properties objective reality. A co-variant second-rank tensor $a_{\mu\nu}$ is symmetric if

$$a_{\mu\nu} \equiv a_{\nu\mu}\tag{4}$$

However, there are circumstances, where a tensor is anti-symmetric. A co-variant second-rank tensor $a_{\mu\nu}$ is anti-symmetric if

$$a_{\mu\nu} \equiv -a_{\nu\mu}\tag{5}$$

Thus far, there are circumstances where an anti-tensor is identical with an anti-symmetrical tensor.

$$a_{\mu\nu} \equiv E_{\mu\nu} - b_{\mu\nu} + \dots \equiv E_{\mu\nu} - \underline{a}_{\mu\nu} \equiv -a_{\nu\mu}\tag{6}$$

Under conditions where $E_{\mu\nu} = 0$, an anti-tensor is identical with an anti-symmetrical tensor or it is

$$-\underline{a}_{\mu\nu} \equiv -a_{\nu\mu}\tag{7}$$

However, an anti-tensor is not identical with an anti-symmetrical tensor as such.

Definition 2.2 (The n-dimensional Pythagorean theorem). *The Pythagorean theorem*

of Euclidean geometry is arguably the most famous statement in mathematics. Besides of the rarity of original sources, the Pythagorean Theorem is attributed to the Greek mathematician and thinker **Pythagoras of Samos** (6th century, B.C.), **the first mathematician**. Meanwhile the Pythagorean Theorem is characterised by more than 371 proofs known. The Pythagorean Theorem is defined by one of the most beautiful equations of mathematics as

$${}_o a_t^2 + {}_o b_t^2 \equiv {}_R C_t^2 \quad (8)$$

where ${}_o$ may denote the point of view of a co-moving observer while ${}_R$ may denote the point of view of a stationary observer at a certain point in space-time ${}_t$. In general, it is

$${}_o a_t^2 \equiv {}_o x_t \times {}_R C_t \quad (9)$$

or

$${}_o a_t^{2n} \equiv {}_o x_t^n \times {}_R C_t^n \quad (10)$$

Equally, it is

$${}_o b_t^2 \equiv {}_o \underline{x}_t \times {}_R C_t \quad (11)$$

or

$${}_o b_t^{2n} \equiv {}_o \underline{x}_t^n \times {}_R C_t^n \quad (12)$$

where n denotes the number of dimensions. The Pythagorean theorem can be extended to higher dimensions [see 60] too. In general, the Pythagorean theorem is based on the fundamental relationship [see 12]

$${}_o x_t + {}_o \underline{x}_t \equiv {}_R C_t \quad (13)$$

In the n dimensional case, this relationship becomes

$$({}_o x_t + {}_o \underline{x}_t)^n \equiv {}_R C_t^n \quad (14)$$

and the n dimensional Pythagorean theorem becomes something like

$$({}_o x_t + {}_o \underline{x}_t)^n \times {}_R C_t^n \equiv {}_R C_t^n \times {}_R C_t^n \quad (15)$$

Remark 2.1. *General relativity is a theory of the geometrical properties of space-time too while the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ itself is of fundamental importance for general relativity. The metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ is something like the generalisation of the Pythagorean theorem. Thus far, it does not appear to be necessary to restrict the validity of the Pythagorean theorem only to certain situations. The question is justified why the Riemannian geometry should be oppressed by the quadratic restriction. In this context, **Finsler geometry**, named after Paul Finsler (1894 - 1970) who studied it in his doctoral thesis [see 28] in 1918, appears to be a kind of a metric generalization of Riemannian geometry without the quadratic restriction and justifies the attempt to systematize and to extend the possibilities of general relativity.*

Definition 2.3 (Multiplication of tensors). *The distance between any two points in a given space can be measured by a kind of a generalized Pythagorean theorem, the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$. Under conditions of general relativity, the metric tensor measures lengths in various directions, and also angles between various directions and is a symmetric rank two tensor and equally more than just a matrix.*

Let g_{kl} or $g_{\mu\nu}$ denote a 2-index metric tensors. Let $g_{kl\mu\nu}$ denote a 4-index metric tensors.

Let $g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots$ denote a n -th index metric tensor. The n -index metric tensor $g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots$ itself is a

covariant symmetric tensor and equally an example of a tensor field. If we pause for a moment today and rely on Einstein's "Die Grundlage der allgemeinen Relativitätstheorie" [see 17, p. 784], it is

$$g_{kl\mu\nu} \equiv g_{kl}g_{\mu\nu} \quad (16)$$

and in the case of n -th rank order

$$g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \equiv g_{kl}g_{\mu\nu} \dots \quad (17)$$

The mixed and contra-variant cases are similar. Riemann defined the distance between two neighbouring points more or less by a quadratic differential form. The geometry based on the positive definite Riemannian metric tensor is called the Riemannian geometry. However, tensor calculus as a generalisation of classical linear algebra should assure that formulae are invariant under coordinate transformations and that the same are independent of any kind of the rank order of the metric tensor chosen.

Figure 1: Einstein. Multiplication of tensors [see 17, p. 784]

Definition 2.4 (Kronecker delta). The Kronecker delta [see 61], a notation invented by Leopold Kronecker (1823-1891) in 1868 [see 36] appears in many areas of physics, mathematics,

and engineering and is defined as

$$g_{\mu\rho} \times g^{\nu\rho} \equiv g_{\mu}^{\nu} \equiv \delta_{\mu}^{\nu} \quad (18)$$

Technically, the Kronecker delta itself is a mixed second-rank tensor.

<p>Nach einem bekannten Determinantensatz ist</p> <p>(16) $g_{\mu\sigma} g^{\nu\sigma} = \delta_{\mu}^{\nu},$</p> <p>wobei das Zeichen δ_{μ}^{ν} 1 oder 0 bedeutet, je nachdem $\mu = \nu$ oder $\mu \neq \nu$ ist. Statt des obigen Ausdruckes für ds^2 können</p>

Figure 2: Einstein. The Kronecker delta (named after Leopold Kronecker) [see 17, p. 787]

The quantity

$$\delta_i^i \equiv \delta_1^1 + \delta_2^2 + \dots + \delta_N^N \equiv N \quad (19)$$

is an invariant.

Definition 2.5 (The metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ and the inverse metric tensor $g^{\mu\nu}$). Einstein described (local) stress-energy and momentum by a tensor $\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}$. In the same respect, the (local) space-time curvature has been described by Einstein as $R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$. Finally, Einstein has been of the opinion that there are conditions where (local) stress-energy and momentum and (local) space-time curvature are related to each other. In general, Einstein field equations relate (local) space-time curvature with (local) energy and momentum by the equation

$$\underbrace{R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})}_{\text{(local) space-time curvature}} \equiv \underbrace{\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}}_{\text{(local) energy and momentum}} \quad (20)$$

The expression on the left side of Einstein field equations represents the curvature of space-time as determined by the metric while the expression on the right side of Einstein field equations

represents the matter–energy content of space-time. Mathematically, it is necessary to consider circumstances that it is possible to take the trace with respect to the metric of both sides of the Einstein field equations. Therefore, we define in general

$$g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} \equiv D \tag{21}$$

where D might denote the number of space-time dimensions. Vectors and scalars are invariant under coordinate transformations. In point of fact, Einstein field equations [22, 17, 23, 21, 19] were initially formulated by Einstein himself in the context of a four-dimensional theory even though Einstein field equations need not to break down under conditions of D space-time dimensions [see 51]. Nonetheless, based on Einstein’s statement [17, p. 796], one gets

$$g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} \equiv D \equiv +4 \tag{22}$$

or

$$\frac{1}{g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu}} \equiv \frac{1}{4} \tag{23}$$

where $g^{\mu\nu}$ is the matrix inverse of the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$. The inverse metric tensor or the metric tensor, which is always symmetric, allow tensors to be transformed into each other and are used to lower and raise indices. Einstein’s point of view is that

“... in the general theory of relativity ... must be ... the tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ of the gravitational potential”

[25, p. 88]

The inverse metric tensor $g^{\mu\nu}$ is of the same size as the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$. Thus far, whatever $g_{\mu\nu}$ does, $g^{\mu\nu}$ undoes and their product is the identity.

Definition 2.6 (The metric tensor of special relativity $\eta_{\mu\nu}$). *There is a fundamental difference between Special and General Relativity regarding the metric tensor. Let $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ denote the metric tensor of Einstein's special theory of relativity. In general, depending upon circumstances,*

it is $\eta_{\mu\nu} = \left\{ \begin{array}{cccc} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & +1 \end{array} \right\}$ [see 17, p. 778]. Let $\underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu}$ denote **the anti-metric tensor**

of Einstein's special theory of relativity. Let $g_{\mu\nu}$ denote the metric tensor of Einstein's general theory of relativity. In general, it is (see definition 2.1, equation 1)

$$g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \eta_{\mu\nu} + \underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu} \quad (24)$$

while the n -th index relationship follows (see definition 2.1, equation 1) as

$$g_{k\ell\mu\nu\dots} \equiv \eta_{k\ell\mu\nu\dots} + \underline{\eta}_{k\ell\mu\nu\dots} \quad (25)$$

Remark 2.2. *Einstein field equations changes according to theorem 3.3, equation 123 $\left(S \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D}\right)\right)$ and equation 24 to*

$$\left(\frac{R}{D} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) + (\Lambda)\right) \times (\eta_{\mu\nu} + \underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times (\eta_{\mu\nu} + \underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu}) \quad (26)$$

From this follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{R}{D} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) + (\Lambda)\right) \times \eta_{\mu\nu} + \left(\frac{R}{D} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) + (\Lambda)\right) \times \underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu} \\ \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times \eta_{\mu\nu} + \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times \underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu} \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

and equally

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \times \eta_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times \eta_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times \eta_{\mu\nu})\right) + \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \times \underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times \underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times \underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu})\right) \\ \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times \eta_{\mu\nu} + \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times \underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu} \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

However, even these equations can be adapted or simplified further

Definition 2.7 (Index raising). According to Einstein [see 17, p. 790] himself or Kay et al. [35], an order-2 tensor, twice multiplied by the contra-variant metric tensor and contracted in different indices raises each index. In simple words, it is

$$F^{\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 3 \\ \mu & c \end{pmatrix}} \equiv g^{\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 \\ \mu & \nu \end{pmatrix}} \times g^{\begin{pmatrix} 3 & 4 \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}} \times F_{\begin{pmatrix} \nu & d \\ 2 & 4 \end{pmatrix}} \quad (29)$$

or more professionally

$$F^{\mu \ c} \equiv g^{\mu\nu} \times g^{cd} \times F_{\nu \ d} \quad (30)$$

Definition 2.8 (The Ricci tensor $\mathbf{R}_{\mu\nu}$). Let $R_{\mu\nu}$ denote the Ricci tensor [45] of ‘Einstein’s general theory of relativity’[17], a geometric object developed by Gregorio Ricci-Curbastro (1853 – 1925) able to measure of the degree to which a certain geometry of a given metric differs from that of ordinary Euclidean space. Let $a_{\mu\nu}$, $b_{\mu\nu}$, $c_{\mu\nu}$ and $d_{\mu\nu}$ denote the four basic fields of nature

Besonders sei auf folgende Bildungen hingewiesen:

$$A^{\mu\nu} = g^{\mu\alpha} g^{\nu\beta} A_{\alpha\beta},$$

$$A_{\mu\nu} = g_{\mu\alpha} g_{\nu\beta} A^{\alpha\beta}$$

(„Ergänzung“ des kovarianten bzw. kontravarianten Tensors)
und

$$B_{\mu\nu} = g_{\mu\alpha} g_{\nu\beta} A^{\alpha\beta}.$$

Wir nennen $B_{\mu\nu}$ den zu $A_{\mu\nu}$ gehörigen reduzierten Tensor.
Analog

$$B^{\mu\nu} = g^{\mu\alpha} g^{\nu\beta} A_{\alpha\beta}.$$

Es sei bemerkt, daß $g^{\mu\nu}$ nichts anderes ist als die Ergänzung
von $g_{\mu\nu}$. Denn man hat

$$g^{\mu\alpha} g^{\nu\beta} g_{\alpha\beta} = g^{\mu\alpha} \delta_{\alpha}^{\nu} = g^{\mu\nu}.$$

Figure 3: Einstein. Index lowering and raising [see 17, p. 790]

were $a_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter, $b_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field.

$$\begin{aligned}
R_{\mu\nu} &\equiv \underbrace{\left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \right)}_{a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu}} + \underbrace{\left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \right)}_{c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}} \\
&\equiv (a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu}) + (c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}) \\
&\equiv (a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu}) + (b_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}) \\
&\equiv (a_{\mu\nu}) + (+b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}) \\
&\equiv (b_{\mu\nu}) + (+a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}) \\
&\equiv (c_{\mu\nu}) + (+a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}) \\
&\equiv (d_{\mu\nu}) + (+a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu}) \\
&\equiv a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu}
\end{aligned} \tag{31}$$

Remark 2.3. In general relativity, it is common to present the Riemann and Ricci tensors by the Christoffel symbols. However, Christoffel symbols are given through the metric tensor itself. Therefore, giving the Ricci tensor while using the metric tensor explicitly, is theoretically possible. **Equation (31)** provide us with one way to present the Ricci tensor in terms of the metric

tensor directly as $R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$.

Definition 2.9 (The Ricci scalar R). Under conditions of Einstein's general [22, 17, 23, 21, 19] theory of relativity, the Ricci scalar curvature R as the trace of the Ricci curvature tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ with respect to the metric is determined at each point in space-time by lamda Λ and anti-lamda [3] $\underline{\Lambda}$ as

$$R \equiv g^{\mu\nu} \times R_{\mu\nu} \equiv (\Lambda) + (\underline{\Lambda}) \equiv D \times X \quad (32)$$

where D is the number of space-time dimension and $X \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D}\right)$ (see theorem 3.3, equation 123). A Ricci scalar curvature R which is positive at a certain point indicates that the volume of a small ball about the point has smaller volume than a ball of the same radius in Euclidean space. In contrast to this, a Ricci scalar curvature R which is negative at a certain point indicates that the volume of a small ball is larger than it would be in Euclidean space. In general it is

$$R \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (\underline{\Lambda} \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (33)$$

The cosmological constant can also be written algebraically as part of the stress–energy tensor, a second order tensor as the source of gravity (energy density).

Definition 2.10 (The stress-energy and momentum tensor $E_{\mu\nu}$). The tensor of stress-energy-momentum denoted as $E_{\mu\nu}$ is determined in detail as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
E_{\mu\nu} &\equiv \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \\
&\equiv G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \\
&\equiv R_{\mu\nu} - \underline{E}_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv H \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv H_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv E \times g_{\mu\nu}
\end{aligned} \tag{34}$$

where E is a scalar. In our understanding, the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field ($b_{\mu\nu}$) is equivalent to the portion of the stress-energy tensor of matter / energy ($E_{\mu\nu}$) due to the electromagnetic field where $T_{\mu\nu}$ “denotes the co-variant energy tensor of matter” [see 25, p. 88]. Importantly, also, and a bit more formally put, Einstein himself elaborates on the fundamental relationship between matter in the narrower sense and the electromagnetic field. *“Considered phenomenologically, this energy tensor is composed of that of the electromagnetic field and of matter in the narrower sense.”* [see 25, p. 93]. The following graphic may illustrate this relationship.

Figure 4. Energy tensor as identity of ordinary matter and electromagnetic field.

However, it is necessary and tricky to explicate the purported tie between classical logic

and relativity theory. In Einstein’s own words, there is no third tensor between the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field ($b_{\mu\nu}$) and the tensor of ordinary matter or matter in the narrower sense ($a_{\mu\nu}$), a third tensor is not given, **tertium non datur**. Aristotle’s law of excluded middle (or the principle of excluded middle), in Latin principium tertii exclusi, is a logical foundation of Einstein’s general theory of relativity. Vranceanu [see 53] is elaborating on the same issue too. In point of fact, the energy tensor T_{kl} is treated by Vranceanu as the sum of two tensors one of which is due to the electromagnetic field ($b_{\mu\nu}$).

“On peut aussi supposer que le tenseur d’énergie T_{kl} soit la somme de deux tenseurs dont un dû au champ électromagnétique . . .” [see 53]

Figure 5. Vranceanu [see 53] .

Translated into English: ‘*One can also assume that the energy tensor T_{kl} be the sum of two tensors one of which is due to the electromagnetic field.*’ In this context, it is necessary to make a distinction between the relationship between ordinary matter and electromagnetic field and matter and gravitational field. Matter and ordinary matter are not completely the same.

Definition 2.11 (Laue’s scalar T). *Max von Laue (1879-1960) proposed the meanwhile so called Laue scalar [37] (criticised by Einstein [26]) as the contraction of the the stress–energy momentum tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ denoted as T and written without subscripts or arguments. Under conditions of Einstein’s general [22, 17, 23, 21, 19] theory of relativity, it is*

$$T \equiv g^{\mu\nu} \times T_{\mu\nu} \tag{35}$$

Taken Einstein seriously, $T_{\mu\nu}$ “denotes the co-variant energy tensor of matter” [see 25, p.

88]. In other words, “Considered phenomenologically, this energy tensor is composed of that of the electromagnetic field and of matter in the narrower sense.”[see 25, p. 93]

Definition 2.12 (The scalar E or H). In general, we define the scalar E or H as

$$\begin{aligned} E \equiv H &\equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times T \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

where D is the space-time dimension, where c denote the speed of the light in vacuum, γ denote Newton’s gravitational “**constant**”[6, 3, 9, 12], π is the number pi and T denote Laue’s scalar. The scalar $E = H$ is corresponding to the total energy of a (relativistic or quantum) system and has the potential as such to bridge the gap between relativity theory and quantum mechanics under circumstances where the same is identical with the Hamiltonian operator.

Definition 2.13 (The 4-index D dimensional stress-energy and momentum tensor $E_{kl\mu\nu}$). The 4-index D dimensional stress-energy-momentum tensor denoted as $E_{kl\mu\nu}$ is determined in detail as

$$\begin{aligned} E_{kl\mu\nu} &\equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv R_{kl\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu}) \\ &\equiv G_{kl\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu}) \\ &\equiv R_{kl\mu\nu} - \underline{E}_{kl\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv a_{kl\mu\nu} + b_{kl\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv H \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \equiv H_{kl\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv E \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

Definition 2.14 (The n-index D dimensional stress-energy and momentum tensor

$\mathbf{E}_{kl\mu\nu \dots}$). The n -index D dimensional stress-energy-momentum tensor denoted as $E_{kl\mu\nu \dots}$ is determined in detail as

$$\begin{aligned}
E_{kl\mu\nu \dots} &\equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu \dots} \\
&\equiv R_{kl\mu\nu \dots} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu \dots} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu \dots}) \\
&\equiv G_{kl\mu\nu \dots} + (\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu \dots}) \\
&\equiv R_{kl\mu\nu \dots} - \underline{E}_{kl\mu\nu \dots} \\
&\equiv a_{kl\mu\nu \dots} + b_{kl\mu\nu \dots} \\
&\equiv H \times g_{kl\mu\nu \dots} \equiv H_{kl\mu\nu \dots} \\
&\equiv E \times g_{kl\mu\nu \dots}
\end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

Definition 2.15 (The tensor of non-energy $\underline{\mathbf{E}}_{\mu\nu}$). Under conditions of Einstein's general [22, 17, 23, 21, 19] theory of relativity, the tensor of non-energy or the anti tensor of the stress energy tensor is defined/derived/determined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\underline{E}_{\mu\nu} &\equiv R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \\
&\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \\
&\equiv c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv \Psi \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \Psi_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv \underline{E} \times g_{\mu\nu}
\end{aligned} \tag{39}$$

Definition 2.16 (The scalar $\underline{\mathbf{E}}$ or \mathbf{t} or Ψ). In general, we define the scalar \underline{E} or t or Ψ as

[see 8]

$$\begin{aligned}
\underline{E} \equiv t \equiv \Psi &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - E \right) \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{40}$$

Remark 2.4. In the following of research it is appropriate to prove the relationship between $(1/X)$ and the complex conjugate of the wave function Ψ^* or the identity $(1/X) \equiv \Psi^*$.

Definition 2.17 (The 4-index D dimensional tensor of non-energy $\underline{E}_{kl\mu\nu}$). The 4-index D dimensional tensor [22, 17, 23, 21, 19] of non-energy $\underline{E}_{kl\mu\nu}$ is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\underline{E}_{kl\mu\nu} &\equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \right) \\
&\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \right) - (\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu}) \\
&\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \right) \\
&\equiv c_{kl\mu\nu} + d_{kl\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv \Psi \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \equiv \Psi_{kl\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv \underline{E} \times g_{kl\mu\nu}
\end{aligned} \tag{41}$$

Definition 2.18 (The n-th index D dimensional tensor of non-energy $\underline{E}_{kl\mu\nu} \dots$). The

n -th index D dimensional tensor [22, 17, 23, 21, 19] of non-energy $\underline{E}_{kl\mu\nu} \dots$ is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\underline{E}_{kl\mu\nu} \dots &\equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \right) - \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \right) \\
&\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \right) - (\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots) \\
&\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \right) \\
&\equiv c_{kl\mu\nu} \dots + d_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \\
&\equiv \Psi \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \equiv \Psi_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \\
&\equiv \underline{E} \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots
\end{aligned} \tag{42}$$

Definition 2.19 (The Einstein's curvature tensor $\mathbf{G}_{\mu\nu}$). Under conditions of Einstein's general [22, 17, 23, 21, 19] theory of relativity, the tensor of curvature denoted by $G_{\mu\nu}$ is defined/derived/determined [see 8] as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\mu\nu} &\equiv R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \\
&\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv G \times g_{\mu\nu}
\end{aligned} \tag{43}$$

Definition 2.20 (The scalar G). *In general, we define the scalar G [8] as*

$$\begin{aligned}
G &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \frac{R}{2} \right) \\
&\equiv \left(E + t - \frac{R}{2} \right) \\
&\equiv \left(E + \left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda \right) - \frac{R}{2} \right) \\
&\equiv E - \Lambda
\end{aligned} \tag{44}$$

Definition 2.21 (The 4-index D dimensional Einstein's curvature tensor $G_{kl\mu\nu}$).

The Riemann tensor $R_{kl\mu\nu}$ does not appear explicitly in Einstein's gravitational field equations. Therefore, the question is justified whether Einstein's equation of gravitation are really the most general equations. Frédéric Moulin proposed in the year 2017 a kind of a generalized 4-index gravitational field equation which contains the Riemann curvature tensor linearly [41]. Moulin himself ascribed an energy-momentum to the gravitational field itself [41, p. 5/8] which is not without problems. Besides of all, it is known that the Riemann curvature tensor of general relativity $R_{kl\mu\nu}$ can be split into different ways, including the Weyl conformal tensor $C_{kl\mu\nu}$ and the anti-Weyl conformal tensor $\underline{C}_{kl\mu\nu}$ or in other words the parts which involve only the Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ the curvature scalar R . Because of these properties ($R_{kl\mu\nu} \equiv C_{kl\mu\nu} + \underline{C}_{kl\mu\nu}$) it is possible to reformulate the famous Einstein equation. The 4-index D dimensional Einstein's curvature tensor [22, 17, 23, 21, 19] denoted by $G_{kl\mu\nu}$ is defined [see 8] as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{kl\mu\nu} &\equiv R_{kl\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \right) \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \right) \\
&\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv a_{kl\mu\nu} + c_{kl\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv G \times g_{kl\mu\nu}
\end{aligned} \tag{45}$$

Definition 2.22 (The n-index D dimensional Einstein's curvature tensor $G_{kl\mu\nu} \dots$).

The n-index D dimensional Einstein's curvature tensor [22, 17, 23, 21, 19] denoted by $G_{kl\mu\nu} \dots$ is defined [see 8] as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{kl\mu\nu} \dots &\equiv R_{kl\mu\nu} \dots - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \right) \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \right) \\
&\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \\
&\equiv a_{kl\mu\nu} \dots + c_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \\
&\equiv G \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots
\end{aligned} \tag{46}$$

Definition 2.23 (The anti Einstein's curvature tensor or the tensor or non-curvature $\underline{G}_{\mu\nu}$). Under conditions of Einstein's general [22, 17, 23, 21, 19] theory of relativity, the tensor of non-curvature is defined/derived/determined [8] as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\underline{G}_{\mu\nu} &\equiv R_{\mu\nu} - G_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv R_{\mu\nu} - \left(R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv b_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv \underline{G} \times g_{\mu\nu}
\end{aligned} \tag{47}$$

Definition 2.24 (The scalar \underline{G}). *In general, we define the scalar \underline{G} [see 8] as*

$$\begin{aligned}
\underline{G} &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - G \right) \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{48}$$

Definition 2.25 (The 4-index D dimensional anti Einstein's curvature tensor or the tensor or non-curvature $\underline{G}_{kl\mu\nu}$). *The 4-index D dimensional anti Einstein's curvature tensor [22, 17, 23, 21, 19] or the tensor of non-curvature denoted as $\underline{G}_{kl\mu\nu}$ is defined/derived/determined [8] as follows:*

$$\begin{aligned}
\underline{G}_{kl\mu\nu} &\equiv R_{kl\mu\nu} - G_{kl\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv R_{kl\mu\nu} - \left(R_{kl\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \right) \right) \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv b_{kl\mu\nu} + d_{kl\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv \underline{G} \times g_{kl\mu\nu}
\end{aligned} \tag{49}$$

Definition 2.26 (The n-index D dimensional anti Einstein's curvature tensor or the

tensor of non-curvature $\underline{G}_{kl\mu\nu \dots}$). The n -index D dimensional anti Einstein's curvature tensor or the tensor of non-curvature denoted as $\underline{G}_{kl\mu\nu \dots}$ is defined/derived/determined [8] as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\underline{G}_{kl\mu\nu \dots} &\equiv R_{kl\mu\nu \dots} - G_{kl\mu\nu \dots} \\
&\equiv R_{kl\mu\nu \dots} - \left(R_{kl\mu\nu \dots} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu \dots} \right) \right) \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu \dots} \\
&\equiv b_{kl\mu\nu \dots} + d_{kl\mu\nu \dots} \\
&\equiv \underline{G} \times g_{kl\mu\nu \dots}
\end{aligned} \tag{50}$$

Definition 2.27 (The stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter $a_{\mu\nu}$). Under conditions of Einstein's general [22, 17, 23, 21, 19] theory of relativity, the stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter $a_{\mu\nu}$ is defined/derived/determined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
a_{\mu\nu} &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \right) - b_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) - b_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv R_{\mu\nu} - (R \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) + d_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv (E - b) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv (G - c) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv a \times g_{\mu\nu}
\end{aligned} \tag{51}$$

or

$$a_{\mu\nu} \equiv R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) - \left(\frac{1}{4 \times \pi} \times \left(\left(F_{\mu c} \times F_{\nu d} \times g^{cd} \right) + \left(\frac{1}{4} \times g_{\mu\nu} \times F_{de} \times F^{de} \right) \right) \right) \quad (52)$$

Definition 2.28 (The 4-index D dimensional $a_{kl\mu\nu}$). The 4-index D dimensional $a_{kl\mu\nu}$ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{kl\mu\nu} &\equiv (E - b) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv (G - c) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv a \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \end{aligned} \quad (53)$$

Definition 2.29 (The n-index D dimensional $a_{kl\mu\nu} \dots$). The n-index D dimensional $a_{kl\mu\nu} \dots$ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{kl\mu\nu} \dots &\equiv (E - b) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \\ &\equiv (G - c) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \\ &\equiv a \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

Definition 2.30 (The first quadratic Lorentz invariant F_1). The inner product of Faraday's electromagnetic field strength tensor yields a Lorentz invariant. The Lorentz invariant does not change from one frame of reference to another. The first quadratic Lorentz invariant, denoted as F_1 is determined as

$$F_1 \equiv F_{kl} \times F^{kl} \quad (55)$$

The electromagnetic field tensor F_{kl} has two Lorentz invariant quantities. One of the two fundamental Lorentz invariant quantities of the electromagnetic field [27] is known be

$F_{kl} \times F^{kl} = 2 \times (B^2 - E^2)$ where E denotes the electric E and B the magnetic field in the taken frame of reference.

Definition 2.31 (The second quadratic Lorentz invariant F_2). *The second quadratic Lorentz invariant, denoted as F_2 is determined as*

$$F_2 \equiv \epsilon^{klmn} \times F_{kl} \times F_{mn} \quad (56)$$

Definition 2.32 (The tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$). *The co-variant Minkowski's stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field, in this context denoted by $b_{\mu\nu}$, is of order two and its components can be displayed by a 4×4 matrix too. The trace of energy-momentum tensor of the electromagnetic field is known to be null. Under conditions of Einstein's general theory of relativity [22, 17, 23, 21, 19], the tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$ denotes the trace-less, symmetric stress-energy tensor for source-free electromagnetic field is defined in cgs-Gaussian units (**depending upon metric signature**) as*

$$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{1}{4 \times \pi} \times \left((F_{\mu c} \times F_{\nu}^c) + \left(\frac{1}{4} \times g_{\mu\nu} \times F_{de} \times F^{de} \right) \right) \right) \quad (57)$$

[see 38, p. 13] and equally as

$$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{1}{4 \times \pi} \times \left((F_{\mu c} \times F_{\nu d} \times g^{cd}) - \left(\frac{1}{4} \times g_{\mu\nu} \times F_{de} \times F^{de} \right) \right) \right) \quad (58)$$

[see 33, p. 38]. *The co-variant Minkowski's stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field is expressed under conditions of $D = 4$ space-time dimensions more compactly in a coordinate-*

independent [theorem 3.1, equation 80 8, p. 157] form as

$$\begin{aligned}
b_{\mu\nu} &\equiv \left(\frac{1}{4 \times \pi} \times \left((F_{\mu c} \times F_{\nu d} \times g^{cd}) + \left(\frac{1}{4} \times g_{\mu\nu} \times F_{de} \times F^{de} \right) \right) \right) \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{1}{4 \times \pi} \times \left((F_{\mu c} \times F^{\mu c}) + \left(\frac{F_1}{4} \right) \right) \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - a - c - d \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv (E - a) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv b \times g_{\mu\nu}
\end{aligned} \tag{59}$$

where F_{de} is called the (traceless) Faraday/electromagnetic/field strength tensor.

Definition 2.33 (The 4-index D dimensional stress-energy tensor of electromagnetic field $\mathbf{b}_{kl\mu\nu}$). The 4-index D dimensional stress-energy tensor of electromagnetic field $b_{kl\mu\nu}$ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
b_{kl\mu\nu} &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - a - c - d \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv (E - a) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv b \times g_{kl\mu\nu}
\end{aligned} \tag{60}$$

Definition 2.34 (The n -index D dimensional stress-energy tensor of electromagnetic field $\mathbf{b}_{kl\mu\nu \dots}$). The n -index D dimensional stress-energy tensor of electromagnetic field $b_{kl\mu\nu \dots}$ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
b_{kl\mu\nu \dots} &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - a - c - d \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu \dots} \\
&\equiv (E - a) \times g_{kl\mu\nu \dots} \\
&\equiv b \times g_{kl\mu\nu \dots}
\end{aligned} \tag{61}$$

Definition 2.35 (The tensor $\mathbf{c}_{\mu\nu}$). Under conditions of Einstein's general [22, 17, 23, 21, 19] theory of relativity, the tensor of non-momentum and curvature is defined/derived/determined

[8] as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
c_{\mu\nu} &\equiv b_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \\
&\equiv (G - a) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda - d\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv (b - \Lambda) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv c \times g_{\mu\nu}
\end{aligned} \tag{62}$$

Definition 2.36 (The 4-index D dimensional tensor $c_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}$). The 4-index D dimensional $c_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}$ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
c_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} &\equiv (G - a) \times g_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda - d\right) \times g_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv (b - \Lambda) \times g_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv c \times g_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}
\end{aligned} \tag{63}$$

Definition 2.37 (The n -index D dimensional tensor $c_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu \dots}$). The n -index D dimensional $c_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu \dots}$ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
c_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu \dots} &\equiv (G - a) \times g_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu \dots} \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda - d\right) \times g_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu \dots} \\
&\equiv (b - \Lambda) \times g_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu \dots} \\
&\equiv c \times g_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu \dots}
\end{aligned} \tag{64}$$

Definition 2.38 (The tensor of neither curvature nor momentum $d_{\mu\nu}$). Under conditions of Einstein's general [22, 17, 23, 21, 19] theory of relativity, the tensor of neither curvature nor momentum is defined/derived/determined [8] as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
d_{\mu\nu} &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - b_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) - c_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times D \right)}{2} - b \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times D \right)}{2} - \Lambda - c \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv d \times g_{\mu\nu}
\end{aligned} \tag{65}$$

There may exist circumstances where this tensor indicates pure vacuum, the space devoid of any matter.

Definition 2.39 (The 4-index D dimensional $d_{kl\mu\nu}$). The 4-index D dimensional $d_{kl\mu\nu}$ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
d_{kl\mu\nu} &\equiv \left(\frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times D \right)}{2} - b \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times D \right)}{2} - \Lambda - c \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv d \times g_{kl\mu\nu}
\end{aligned} \tag{66}$$

Definition 2.40 (The n -index D dimensional $d_{kl\mu\nu} \dots$). The n -index D dimensional

$d_{kl\mu\nu} \dots$ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
d_{kl\mu\nu} \dots &\equiv \left(\frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times D \right)}{2} - b \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times D \right)}{2} - \Lambda - c \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \\
&\equiv d \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots
\end{aligned} \tag{67}$$

Table 1 provides an overview of the general definition of the relationships between the four basic [12, 11] fields of nature under conditions of the general theory of relativity.

		Curvature		
		YES	NO	
Momentum	YES	$a_{\mu\nu}$	$b_{\mu\nu}$	$E_{\mu\nu}$
	NO	$c_{\mu\nu}$	$d_{\mu\nu}$	$\underline{E}_{\mu\nu}$
		$G_{\mu\nu}$	$\underline{G}_{\mu\nu}$	$R_{\mu\nu}$

Table 1: Einstein field equations and the four basic fields of nature

Definition 2.41 (The Einstein field equations). Let $R_{\mu\nu}$ denote the Ricci tensor [45] of ‘Einstein’s general theory of relativity’[17], a geometric object developed by Gregorio Ricci-Curbastro (1853 – 1925) able to measure of the degree to which a certain geometry of a given metric differs from that of ordinary Euclidean space. Let R denote the Ricci scalar, the trace of the Ricci curvature tensor with respect to the metric and equally the simplest curvature invariant of a Riemannian manifold. Ricci scalar curvature is the contraction of the Ricci tensor and is written as R without subscripts or arguments. Let Λ denote the Einstein’s cosmological constant. Let $\underline{\Lambda}$ denote the “**anti cosmological constant**”[3]. Let $g_{\mu\nu}$ metric tensor of Einstein’s general theory of relativity. Let $G_{\mu\nu}$ denote Einstein’s curvature tensor. Let $\underline{G}_{\mu\nu}$ denote the “**anti tensor**”[12] of Einstein’s curvature tensor. Let $E_{\mu\nu}$ denote stress-energy tensor of energy. Let $\underline{E}_{\mu\nu}$ denote tensor of non-energy, the anti-tensor of the stress-energy tensor of energy. Let $a_{\mu\nu}$, $b_{\mu\nu}$, $c_{\mu\nu}$ and $d_{\mu\nu}$ denote the four basic fields of nature were $a_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of

ordinary matter, $b_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field. Let c denote the speed of the light in vacuum, let γ denote Newton's gravitational "constant" [6, 3, 9, 12]. Let π denote the number pi. Einstein's field equation, published by Albert Einstein [22] for the first time in 1915, and finally 1916 [17] but later with the "cosmological constant" [23, 21, 19] term are determined as

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (68)$$

$$\equiv E_{\mu\nu}$$

However, the above left-hand side of the Einstein field equations represents only one part (Ricci curvature) of the geometric structure (Weyl curvature).

Table 2 provides a more detailed overview of the definitions of the four basic [12, 11] fields of nature.

		Curvature		
		YES	NO	
Momentum	YES	$a_{\mu\nu}$	$b_{\mu\nu}$	$\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \times T_{\mu\nu}$
	NO	$(b_{\mu\nu} - \Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$	$(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu} - b_{\mu\nu})$	$(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu} - \Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$
		$G_{\mu\nu}$	$\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}$	$R_{\mu\nu}$

Table 2: Einstein field equations and the four basic fields of nature

Remark 2.5. *There are manifolds where the stress-energy tensor arise entirely from an electromagnetic field with the consequence that the only source for the gravitational field is the field energy (and momentum) of the electromagnetic field. Such manifolds are characterized by the condition that $a_{\mu\nu} = 0$ (electrovacuum solutions). However, among the many well-known exact solutions in general relativity is the lambdavacuum solution too, which is distinct from*

electrovacuum and vacuum solutions. In general, $T_{\mu\nu}$ contains **all** forms of energy, momentum et cetera which includes any matter present but if there is some electromagnetic radiation then it to must be included in $T_{\mu\nu}$. However, regions of space-time devoid of any matter but also of radiative energy and momentum were $T_{\mu\nu} = 0$ (i. e. in a vacuum region) might exist. Under conditions were $\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \equiv 0$ the Einstein field equations becomes

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \equiv 0 \quad (69)$$

or

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv 0 \quad (70)$$

Considering Ricci-flat manifolds, manifolds with a vanishing Ricci tensor, $R_{\mu\nu} = 0$, an equivalent formulation of the relationship above follows as

$$0 - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv 0 \quad (71)$$

Equation 71 simplifies as

$$\left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) \equiv (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (72)$$

Manipulating equation 72 it is

$$\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \equiv (\Lambda) \quad (73)$$

or

$$R \equiv 2 \times (\Lambda) \equiv (\Lambda) + (\Lambda) \quad (74)$$

Rearranging equation 74, it is

$$R - (\Lambda) \equiv (\Lambda) \quad (75)$$

Under conditions where $T_{\mu\nu} = 0$ (i. e. in a vacuum region) and $R_{\mu\nu} = 0$ (Ricci-flat manifolds), equation 75 simplifies (see theorem 3.18, equation 258) as

$$\underline{\Lambda} \equiv \Lambda \quad (76)$$

Under conditions where the Ricci scalar itself is equal to $R = 0$, equation 75 changes to

$$-\Lambda \equiv +\Lambda \quad (77)$$

and the state of pure symmetry, a possible state nature before the beginning of this world, is given. In other words, a nonzero cosmological constant can be positive (as in de Sitter space, named after Willem de Sitter (1872–1934) [see 50, 49]) or negative (as in anti-de Sitter space). Thus far, has this world developed out of the state of pure symmetry (equation 77) where

$$(anti-de Sitter space) = (de Sitter space)$$

is one among the many far-reaching questions which might follow from equation 77. Nonetheless, equation 75 changes under conditions of manifolds where $T_{\mu\nu} = 0$ and $R_{\mu\nu} = 0$. In general, manifolds where $T_{\mu\nu} = 0$ and $R_{\mu\nu} = 0$ are determined according to the definition 2.9, equation 32, by the equation

$$\underline{\Lambda} \equiv \Lambda \quad (78)$$

Rearranging equation 70 it is

$$G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv 0 \quad (79)$$

or

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \equiv -(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (80)$$

An equivalent formulation of the exact lambdavacuum solutions in general relativity in terms of the Ricci tensor is given by

$$R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (81)$$

Table 3 provides an overview of Einstein field equations and the lambdavacuum solution [12, 11].

	Curvature		
	YES	NO	
Momentum YES	0	0	0
NO	$(-\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$	$(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu})$	$(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu} - \Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$
	$G_{\mu\nu}$	$\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}$	$R_{\mu\nu}$

Table 3: Einstein field equations and the lambdavacuum solution

2.2. Axioms

2.2.1. Axioms in general Axioms [32] and rules which are chosen carefully can be of use to avoid logical inconsistency and equally preventing science from supporting particular ideologies. Rightly or wrongly, long lasting advances in our knowledge of nature are enabled by suitable axioms [16] too.

2.2.2. Axiom I. Lex identitatis To say that +1 is identical to +1 is to say that both are the same.

Axiom 1. Lex identitatis.

$$+ 1 \equiv +1 \quad (82)$$

2.2.3. Axiom II. Lex contradictionis **Axiom 2. Lex contradictionis.**

$$+ 0 \equiv +1 \quad (83)$$

2.2.4. *Axiom III. Lex negationis* **Axiom 3. Lex negationis.**

$$\neg(0) \times (+0) \equiv (+1) \quad (84)$$

where \neg denotes the (natural/logical) process of negation.

3. Results

3.1. The n -dimensional Pythagorean theorem

Theorem 3.1 (The n -dimensional Pythagorean theorem). *The Pythagorean theorem as attributed to the Greek thinker Pythagoras of Samos (6th century, B.C.) is defined as*

$${}_o a_t^2 + {}_o b_t^2 \equiv {}_R C_t^2 \quad (85)$$

where ${}_o$ may denote the point of view of a co-moving observer while ${}_R$ may denote the point of view of a stationary observer at a certain point in space-time t .

In general, the n -dimensional Pythagorean theorem is given by the equation

$$\left(({}_o a_t^2) + ({}_o b_t^2) \right)^n \equiv {}_R C_t^{2n} \quad (86)$$

Proof by modus ponens. **If** the premise

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{(Premise)} \quad (87)$$

is true, **then** the conclusion

$$((\textcircled{a}_t^2) + (\textcircled{b}_t^2))^n \equiv_{\mathbb{R}} C_t^{2n} \quad (88)$$

is also true, the absence of any technical errors presupposed. The premise

$$(+1) = (+1) \quad (89)$$

is true. Multiplying this premise by x_t it is

$$x_t \equiv x_t \quad (90)$$

Adding \textcircled{x}_t to equation 90 it is

$$x_t + \textcircled{x}_t \equiv x_t + \textcircled{x}_t \quad (91)$$

Equation 91 changes (see definition 2.2, equation 13) to

$$x_t + \textcircled{x}_t \equiv_{\mathbb{R}} C_t \quad (92)$$

which is equally the general foundation of the Pythagorean theorem [see 12]. However, the Pythagorean theorem can be extended to higher dimensions [see 60] too. In the n-dimensional

case, equation 92 becomes

$$({}_o x_t + {}_o \underline{x}_t)^n \equiv \left(\underbrace{({}_o x_t + {}_o \underline{x}_t) \times ({}_o x_t + {}_o \underline{x}_t) \times ({}_o x_t + {}_o \underline{x}_t) \times \dots}_{n \text{ times}} \right) \equiv {}_R C_t^n \quad (93)$$

Multiplying equation 93 by the term ${}_R C_t^n$ we obtain

$$(({}_o x_t + {}_o \underline{x}_t)^n) \times {}_R C_t^n \equiv \left(\underbrace{({}_o x_t + {}_o \underline{x}_t) \times ({}_o x_t + {}_o \underline{x}_t) \times ({}_o x_t + {}_o \underline{x}_t) \times \dots}_{n \text{ times}} \right) \times {}_R C_t^n \equiv {}_R C_t^n \times {}_R C_t^n \quad (94)$$

Equation 94 simplifies as

$$(({}_o x_t + {}_o \underline{x}_t)^n) \times {}_R C_t^n \equiv ({}_o x_t + {}_o \underline{x}_t) \times {}_R C_t^n \equiv (({}_o x_t \times {}_R C_t) + ({}_o \underline{x}_t \times {}_R C_t))^n \equiv {}_R C_t^{2n} \quad (95)$$

In general, it is ${}_o a_t^2 \equiv {}_o x_t \times {}_R C_t$ (see definition 2.2, equation 9). Equation 95 simplifies as

$$(({}_o a_t^2) + ({}_o \underline{x}_t \times {}_R C_t))^n \equiv {}_R C_t^{2n} \quad (96)$$

Furthermore, it is ${}_o b_t^2 \equiv {}_o \underline{x}_t \times {}_R C_t$ (see definition 2.2, equation 11). The n-dimensional Pythagorean theorem follows as

$$(({}_o a_t^2) + ({}_o b_t^2))^n \equiv {}_R C_t^{2n} \quad (97)$$

In other words, our conclusion is true.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Remark 3.1. *The make a long story short, the Pythagorean theorem is defined as*

$${}_o a_t^2 + {}_o b_t^2 \equiv {}_R C_t^2 \quad (98)$$

Raising to the power n , the n dimensional Pythagorean theorem is given as

$$\left(({}_o a_t^2) + ({}_o b_t^2) \right)^n \equiv {}_R C_t^{2n} \quad (99)$$

It follows from equation 99 the normalised n dimensional Pythagorean theorem as

$$\left(\frac{{}_o a_t^{2n}}{{}_R C_t^{2n}} \right) + \left(\frac{{}_R C_t^{2n} - {}_o a_t^{2n}}{{}_R C_t^{2n}} \right) \equiv \left(\frac{{}_R C_t^{2n}}{{}_R C_t^{2n}} \right) \equiv +1 \quad (100)$$

Fermat's Last Theorem states that $({}_o a_t^n) + ({}_o b_t^n) \equiv {}_R C_t^n$ while no three positive integers a , b , and c satisfy the equation for any integer value of n greater than 2. Rearranging Fermat's Last Theorem, we obtain

$$\left(({}_o a_t^n) + ({}_o b_t^n) \right)^2 \equiv ({}_R C_t^n)^2 \quad (101)$$

while a lot of positive integers ${}_o a_t$, ${}_o b_t$, and ${}_R C_t$ satisfy equation 101 for any integer value of n (and even greater than 2). Simplifying equation 101 leads to a more general form of the equation before as

$$\left(({}_o a_t^{2n}) + (2 \times {}_o a_t^n \times {}_o b_t^n) + ({}_o b_t^{2n}) \right) \equiv ({}_R C_t^{2n}) \quad (102)$$

and Fermat's Last Theorem appears to pass over into the n dimensional Pythagorean theorem. The metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ of general relativity on a space is more or less a generalisation of Pythagoras' theorem for the distance for a certain distance between two points separated by different distances and reproduces the usual form of the Pythagorean Theorem. In general it is

$$g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu \equiv ds^2 \quad (103)$$

while reproducing the usual form of the Pythagorean Theorem. The n dimensional form follows

as

$$(g_{\mu\nu}dx^\mu dx^\nu)^n \equiv (ds^2)^n \equiv ({}_R C_t^{2n}) \quad (104)$$

3.2. Refutation of Fermat's Last Theorem

Theorem 3.2 (Refutation of Fermat's Last Theorem). *Fermat's last theorem known as $({}_o a_t^n) + ({}_o b_t^n) \equiv {}_R C_t^n$ while no three positive integers a , b , and c satisfy the equation for any integer value of n greater than 2, is refuted.*

Proof by modus ponens. **If** the premise

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{(Premise)} \quad (105)$$

is true, **then** the conclusion

$$({}_o b_t^n) \equiv {}_R C_t^n \quad (106)$$

is also true, the absence of any technical errors presupposed, and Fermat's last theorem is refuted. The premise

$$+ 1 \equiv +1 \quad (107)$$

is true. Multiplying this premise (i. e. axiom or equation 107) by ${}_R C_t^n$, it is

$$+ 1 \times {}_R C_t^n \equiv +1 \times {}_R C_t^n \quad (108)$$

or

$${}_R C_t^n \equiv {}_R C_t^n \quad (109)$$

Pierre de Fermat's (1607 - 1665) Last Theorem (i. e. Observatio Domini Petri de Fermat)

published 1670 in the book *Diophantus's Arithmetica* by Fermat's son, often considered simply as one of the most notable unsolved problems of mathematics, states that $({}_o a_t^n) + ({}_o b_t^n) \equiv_R C_t^n$ while no three positive integers a , b , and c satisfy the equation for any integer value of n greater than 2. Equation 109 changes to

$$({}_o a_t^n) + ({}_o b_t^n) \equiv_R C_t^n \quad (110)$$

Investigating the behaviour of **Fermat's Last Theorem** under conditions where $\mathbf{a} = +0$, we obtain

$$((a_t \equiv +0)^n) + ({}_o b_t^n) \equiv_R C_t^n \quad (111)$$

or

$$({}_o b_t^n) \equiv_R C_t^n \quad (112)$$

In other words, at least one integer, the positive zero, is in compliance with Fermat's Last Theorem. Consequently, Fermat's Last Theorem is refuted. *Quod erat demonstrandum.*

Remark 3.2. *Andrew Wiles's 1995 corrected proof of Fermat's Last Theorem [see 57] appears to be none or of a limited value. Three distinct positive integers ($a = +0$), b , and c can satisfy Fermat's equation*

$$({}_o a_t^n) + ({}_o b_t^n) \equiv_R C_t^n \quad (113)$$

has a solutions in positive integers for $n \geq 3$. However, there is justified reason to believe that it will be disputed that the positive zero ($+0$) is an integer. Well, in this case, a clear and convincing answer should be given to the question why a positive zero is not an integer. What than is a positive zero, a non-integer, an anti-integer or ...?

Theorem 3.3 (The relationship between the Ricci scalar R and the number of dimensions of

space-time D). *Einstein Field Equations are defined in space-time dimensions [see 40, p. 31] other than 3+1 too.*

In general, the scalar S is given by

$$X \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \quad (114)$$

*Proof by modus ponens. **If** the premise*

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{(Premise)} \quad (115)$$

is true, **then** the conclusion

$$S \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \quad (116)$$

is also true, the absence of any technical errors presupposed. The premise

$$(+1) = (+1) \quad (117)$$

is true. Multiplying this premise by Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ it is

$$R_{\mu\nu} \equiv R_{\mu\nu} \quad (118)$$

Theoretically, it is possible to express the Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ mathematically completely through the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ in an easy and straightforward way. In general, we define the Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ as being completely determined by a scalar X and the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ as

$$R_{\mu\nu} \equiv X \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (119)$$

However, at this stage, we just don't know the exact value of the scalar X . Rearranging it is,

$$R_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} \equiv X \times g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} \quad (120)$$

or in accordance to definition 2.9

$$R \equiv X \times g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} \quad (121)$$

According to definition 2.5 (definition 2.5, equation 21) it is

$$R \equiv X \times D \quad (122)$$

In general, the scalar X is depending on the number of space-time dimensions D and it is

$$X \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \quad (123)$$

In other words, our conclusion is true.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Remark 3.3. *The complete geometrization of Einstein field equations as provided by Ilija Barukčić [see 8] has been derived under conditions where the number of space-time dimensions D is equal to $D = 4$.*

Theorem 3.4 (The Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ given through the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ under conditions of D space-time dimensions.). *In general relativity, it is common to present the Riemann and Ricci tensors using the Christoffel symbols while Christoffel symbols are given through the metric. Mathematical formulas giving the Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ under conditions of D space-time dimensions [see 40, p. 31] while using explicitly the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ are missing.*

In general, the Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ is given by the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ as

$$R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (124)$$

where D is the number of space-time dimensions.

Proof by modus ponens. **If** the premise

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{(Premise)} \quad (125)$$

is true, **then** the conclusion

$$R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{D} \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (126)$$

is also true, the absence of any technical errors presupposed. The premise

$$(+1) = (+1) \quad (127)$$

is true. Multiplying this premise by the Ricci scalar R it is

$$R \equiv R \quad (128)$$

According to theorem 3.3, equation 122, the equation before (equation 128) is equivalent with

$$X \times D \equiv R \quad (129)$$

Rearranging, we obtain

$$X \equiv \frac{R}{D} \quad (130)$$

Multiplying by the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$, it is

$$X \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{D} \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (131)$$

According to theorem 3.3, equation 119 it is $R_{\mu\nu} \equiv X \times g_{\mu\nu}$. The Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ expressed directly in terms of the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ under conditions of D space-time dimensions follows as

$$R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (132)$$

In other words, our conclusion is true.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Remark 3.4. *Einstein's general theory of relativity does not in any way privilege a particular space-time geometry. In this context, the string theory is a theoretical framework in which particles of particle physics are replaced by strings, a kind of one-dimensional objects and is treated more or less as not manifestly background independent. Under conditions of $D = 1$ space-time dimensions (see theorem 3.4, equation 132) it is $R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{1} \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv R \times g_{\mu\nu}$ while the background independent Einstein field equations changes to $\left(\frac{R}{1} \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times 1} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$ or to $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$. Under conditions of $D = 2$ space-time dimensions (see theorem 3.4, equation 132) it is necessary to consider the possibility that $R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}$ while the Einstein field equations changes to $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times 2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$ or to $\left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{4 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$. In particular, under conditions of $D = 3$ space-time dimensions (see theorem 3.4, equation 132) we obtain $R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{3} \times g_{\mu\nu}$ while the Einstein field equations changes*

to $\left(\frac{R}{3} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times 3}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$. Under conditions of original general relativity ($D = 4$ space-time dimensions), it is (see theorem 3.4, equation 132) $R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{4} \times g_{\mu\nu}$ while the Einstein field equations changes to $\left(\frac{R}{4} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times 4}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$. The Kaluza–Klein theory [34] is a kind of a historical precursor of string theory and equally a classical unified field theory of gravitation and electromagnetism built around fifth dimension which used a similar idea of Gunnar Nordström. Nordström suggested: “Es wird gezeigt, daß eine einheitliche Behandlung des elektromagnetischen Feldes und des Gravitationsfeldes möglich ist, wenn man die vierdimensionale Raumzeitwelt als eine durch eine fünfdimensionale Welt gelegte Fläche auffaßt. “[43]. Under conditions of $D = 5$ space-time dimensions (Kaluza–Klein theory), it is (see theorem 3.4, equation 132) $R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{5} \times g_{\mu\nu}$ while the Einstein field equations changes to $\left(\frac{R}{5} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times 5}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$. In string theory, space-time is ten-dimensional (nine spatial dimensions, and one time dimension) and it is $R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{10} \times g_{\mu\nu}$ while the Einstein field equations changes to $\left(\frac{R}{10} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times 10}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$. In the year 1995, Edward Witten [see 59] suggested that the five consistent versions of superstring theory (type I, type IIA, type IIB, and two versions of heterotic string theory) were just special limiting cases of an eleven-dimensional theory called M-theory. In M-theory space-time is eleven-dimensional (ten spatial dimensions, and one time dimension). Under conditions of M-theory ($D = 11$ space-time dimensions), it is (see theorem 3.4, equation 132) $R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{11} \times g_{\mu\nu}$ while the Einstein field equations changes to $\left(\frac{R}{11} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times 11}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$. For now there is no end in sight on the number of space-time dimensions D and the theories associated with the same. Under conditions of a 4-index or n -th index metric tensor, the formulas need to be adopted like $\left(\frac{R}{11} \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times 11}\right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots$

Theorem 3.5 (The Riemann curvature tensor or Riemann–Christoffel tensor $R_{kl\mu\nu}$ given explicitly through the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ under conditions of D space-time dimensions). *The*

Riemann curvature tensor (named after Georg Friedrich Bernhard Riemann (1826 - 1866) and Elwin Bruno Christoffel (1829 -1900)) is more or less a central mathematical tool in the theory of general relativity [46, 47]. The Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ itself is a contraction of the Riemann curvature tensor but can be viewed as something like a 2-index Riemann curvature tensor and vice versa. The Riemann curvature tensor can be viewed as an 4-index Ricci tensor.

In general, the Riemann curvature tensor $R_{kl\mu\nu}$ is given by the metric tensor $g_{kl\mu\nu}$ as

$$R_{kl\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \times g_{kl} \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv X \times g_{kl} \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \quad (133)$$

where D is the number of space-time dimensions.

Proof by modus ponens. **If** the premise

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{(Premise)} \quad (134)$$

is true, **then** the conclusion

$$R_{kl\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \times g_{kl} \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv X \times g_{kl} \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \quad (135)$$

(see definition 2.3, equation 16) is also true, the absence of any technical errors presupposed.

The premise

$$(+1) = (+1) \quad (136)$$

is true. Multiplying this premise by the Ricci scalar R it is

$$R \equiv R \quad (137)$$

According to theorem 3.3, equation 122, the equation before (equation 128) is equivalent with

$$X \times D \equiv R \quad (138)$$

Rearranging, we obtain

$$X \equiv \frac{R}{D} \quad (139)$$

Multiplying equation 139 by the metric tensor g_{kl} and the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$, it is

$$X \times g_{kl} \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{D} \times g_{kl} \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (140)$$

According to definition 2.3, equation 16 it is $g_{kl\mu\nu} \equiv g_{kl} \times g_{\mu\nu}$. We obtain

$$X \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{D} \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \quad (141)$$

The Riemann curvature tensor or Riemann–Christoffel tensor $R_{kl\mu\nu}$ expressed directly in terms of the metric tensor $g_{kl\mu\nu}$ under conditions of D space-time dimensions follows as

$$R_{kl\mu\nu} \equiv X \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{D} \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \quad (142)$$

In other words, our conclusion is true.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Theorem 3.6 (The n-th index Riemann curvature tensor or Riemann–Christoffel tensor $R_{kl\mu\nu} \dots$ given explicitly through the metric tensor $g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots$ under conditions of D space-time dimensions). *The n-th index Riemann curvature tensor or Riemann–Christoffel tensor $R_{kl\mu\nu} \dots$ given explicitly through the n-th index metric tensor $g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots$ under conditions of D space-time*

dimensions is determined as

$$R_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \equiv X \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \quad (143)$$

Proof. It is (see theorem 3.3, equation 123)

$$X \equiv \frac{R}{D} \quad (144)$$

Multiplying by the metric tensor $g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots$ we obtain

$$R_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \equiv X \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \equiv \frac{R}{D} \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \quad (145)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Remark 3.5. In general, it is $R_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \equiv X \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \equiv \frac{R}{D} \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots$. Taking the trace, it is $R_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \times g^{kl\mu\nu} \dots \equiv X \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \times g^{kl\mu\nu} \dots \equiv \frac{R}{D} \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \times g^{kl\mu\nu} \dots$. Since $D \equiv g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \times g^{kl\mu\nu} \dots$ we obtain $X \equiv \frac{R}{D}$ and our conclusion is true. The situation is not quite different if analysed from another point of view. As found, it is $R_{kl\mu\nu} \equiv X \times g_{kl} \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{D} \times g_{kl} \times g_{\mu\nu}$. Rearranging, we obtain $R_{kl\mu\nu} \times g^{kl} \equiv X \times g_{kl} \times g^{kl} \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{D} \times g_{kl} \times g^{kl} \times g_{\mu\nu}$ or $R_{\mu\nu} \equiv X \times D_1 \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{D} \times D_1 \times g_{\mu\nu}$. Rearranging again, we obtain $R_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} \equiv X \times D_1 \times g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{D} \times D_1 \times g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu}$ or $R \equiv X \times D_1 \times D_2 \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \times D_1 \times D_2$. Since $R = R$, it is necessary to accept that $D \equiv D_1 \times D_2$ or in general $D \equiv D_1 \times D_2 \times \dots$.

Theorem 3.7 (The relationship between the scalar E and the number of dimensions of space-time D). *Einstein field Equations in other space-time dimensions [see 40, p. 31] than 3+1 need not lead to insurmountable contradictions.*

In general, the scalar E is determined as

$$E \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \quad (146)$$

Proof by modus ponens. **If** the premise

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{(Premise)} \quad (147)$$

is true, **then** the conclusion

$$E \equiv \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \quad (148)$$

is also true, the absence of any technical errors presupposed. The premise (i. e axiom)

$$(+1) = (+1) \quad (149)$$

is true. Multiplying this premise by the stress-energy momentum tensor it is

$$\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (150)$$

We do expect that the stress-energy momentum tensor can be geometrized completely as

$$\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \equiv E \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (151)$$

Rearranging it is,

$$\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} \equiv E \times g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} \quad (152)$$

According to definition of Laue's scalar (definition 2.11) it is

$$\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T \equiv E \times g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} \quad (153)$$

According to definition 2.5, equation 21 it is

$$\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4}\right) \equiv E \times D \quad (154)$$

The scalar E is depending on the number of space-time dimensions D and is given in general as

$$E \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \quad (155)$$

In other words, our conclusion is true.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Theorem 3.8 (The 2-index stress-energy-momentum tensor of matter under conditions of D space-time dimensions). *The starting point of Einstein's theory of general relativity is that gravity as such is a property of space-time geometry. Consequently, Einstein published a geometric theory of gravitation [17] while Einstein's initial hope to construct a purely geometric theory of gravitation in which even the sources of gravitation themselves would be of geometric origin has still not been fulfilled. Einstein's field equations have a source term, the stress-energy tensor of matter, radiation and vacuum et cetera, which is of order two and is still devoid of any geometry and free of any geometrical significance. In general, the completely geometrical form of the 2-index stress-energy momentum tensor of Einstein's theory of general relativity under conditions*

of D space-time dimensions is given by

$$\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times \left(\frac{T}{D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (156)$$

Proof by modus ponens. **If** the premise

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{(Premise)} \quad (157)$$

is true, **then** the conclusion

$$\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times \left(\frac{T}{D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (158)$$

is also true, the absence of any technical errors presupposed. The premise

$$(+1) = (+1) \quad (159)$$

is true. Multiplying this premise by Einstein's stress-energy-momentum tensor of matter

$\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}$ it is

$$\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (160)$$

Again, it is possible to express the stress-energy-momentum tensor of matter completely in terms

of the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$. We obtain

$$E_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \equiv E \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (161)$$

According to theorem 3.7, equation 155, equation 161 can be simplified. The stress-energy-momentum tensor of matter under conditions of D space-time dimensions is determined by the equation

$$E_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \equiv E \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times \left(\frac{T}{D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (162)$$

where D is the number of space-time dimensions.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Remark 3.6. *Theorem 3.8, equation 162 demands that*

$$\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times \left(\frac{T}{D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (163)$$

This equation leads straightforward to the need that

$$T_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{T}{D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (164)$$

Lemma 3.1. *It is*

$$\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times \left(\frac{T}{D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (165)$$

Simplifying equation 165, the most simple geometrical form of the pure 2-index stress-energy

momentum tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ under conditions of D dimensions is determined by the equation

$$T_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{T}{D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (166)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Remark 3.7. In more detail, under conditions of $D = 4$ dimensions the pure 2-index stress–energy momentum tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ is determined by the metric, enriched only by view constants and a scalar T as

$$\left(\frac{2 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (167)$$

However, describing the fundamental stress–energy momentum tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$, the source term of the gravitational field in Einstein’s general theory of relativity, as an inherent geometrical structure, as being determined and dependent on the metric field $g_{\mu\nu}$ is associated with several and far reaching consequences. Theoretically, it is possible that the properties of energy, momentum, mass, stress et cetera need no longer to be treated or understood as intrinsic properties of matter as such. Following equation 167, the properties which material systems posses could be determined in virtue of their relation to space-time structures too. In last consequence, the question might arise whether the energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ at the end could be in different aspects less fundamental than the metric field $g_{\mu\nu}$ itself. Is and why is matter more fundamental [38, 39] than space-time? In contrast to such a position, is the assumption justified that **without** the space-time structure encoded in the metric **no** energy (tensor)? To bring it to the point, can space-time (and its geometric structure) exist without matter and if yes, what kind of existence could this be? Einstein’s starting point was to derive space-time structure from the properties of material systems. In contrast such a position, theorem 3.8 allow us to consider that the energy tensor might depend on the metric field or in an extreme case is completely determined by the metric field. In extreme circumstances, the matter fields themselves are potentially derivable

from the structure of space-time or the very definition of an energy tensor is determined by space-time structures too. Thus far, the question is not answered definitely, which came first, either space-time structure or energy (tensor). So it is reasonable to ask, whether the energy-momentum tensor of matter is dependent on the structures of space-time or only mathematically described by the structures of space-time or both or none? In other words, granddaddies **either the hen and the egg** dilemma is asking for a new, innovative and comprehensive solution and may end up in an Anti-Machian theory. However, this leads us at this point too far afield.

Theorem 3.9 (The 4-index stress-energy-momentum tensor of matter $T_{kl\mu\nu}$ under conditions of D space-time dimensions completely geometrized). *The very detailed discussion of the various proposals for a unified field theory can be found in secondary literature [29] too. Nevertheless, it seems to us that the theory of general relativity taken as the point of departure for unified field theory has at least one weak spot. Einstein's stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ is more or less a field devoid of any geometrical significance. In view of the missing geometrization of the source of gravitation in the Einstein field equations any logically consistent development of a unified field theory more geometrico is endangered. The 4-index D dimensional stress-energy and momentum tensor $E_{kl\mu\nu}$ follows as (see definition 2.13, equation 37)*

$$E_{kl\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \quad (168)$$

Proof by modus ponens. **If** the premise of modus ponens

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{(Premise)} \quad (169)$$

is true, **then** the following conclusion

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\text{kl}\mu\nu} &\equiv E \times g_{\text{kl}\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{\text{kl}\mu\nu} \end{aligned} \quad (170)$$

is also true. The premise (+1 = +1) is true. A further manipulation of the premise (+1 = +1) yields the result (see theorem 3.7, equation 155)

$$E \equiv \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \quad (171)$$

Multiplying equation 171 by the 4-index metric tensor $g_{\text{kl}\mu\nu}$, it is

$$E \times g_{\text{kl}\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{\text{kl}\mu\nu} \quad (172)$$

The 4-index D dimensional stress-energy and momentum tensor $E_{\text{kl}\mu\nu}$ follows (see definition 2.13, equation 37) as

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\text{kl}\mu\nu} &\equiv E \times g_{\text{kl}\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{\text{kl}\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv R_{\text{kl}\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\text{kl}\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\text{kl}\mu\nu}) \end{aligned} \quad (173)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Theorem 3.10 (The n-index stress-energy-momentum tensor of matter $T_{\text{kl}\mu\nu} \dots$ under conditions of D space-time dimensions completely geometrized). *The n-th index stress-energy-momentum tensor of matter $T_{\text{kl}\mu\nu}$ has already been discussed in literature [41]. However, it is possible and necessary to go even beyond 4-index stress-energy-momentum tensor of matter $T_{\text{kl}\mu\nu}$. The n-th index stress-energy-momentum tensor of matter $T_{\text{kl}\mu\nu} \dots$ under conditions of D*

space-time dimensions completely geometrized follows (see definition 2.13, equation 37) as

$$E_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \quad (174)$$

Proof by modus ponens. **If** the premise of modus ponens

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{(Premise)} \quad (175)$$

is true, **then** the following conclusion

$$\begin{aligned} E_{kl\mu\nu} \dots &\equiv E \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \end{aligned} \quad (176)$$

is also true. The premise (+1 = +1) is true. A further manipulation of the premise (+1 = +1) yields the result (see theorem 3.7, equation 155)

$$E \equiv \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \quad (177)$$

Multiplying equation 177 by the n-index metric tensor $g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots$, it is

$$E \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \equiv \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \quad (178)$$

The n-index D dimensional stress-energy and momentum tensor $E_{kl\mu\nu} \dots$ follows (see definition

2.13, equation 37) as

$$\begin{aligned}
E_{kl\mu\nu} \dots &\equiv E \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \\
&\equiv R_{kl\mu\nu} \dots - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots)
\end{aligned} \tag{179}$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Theorem 3.11 (The geometrical form of the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field $\mathbf{b}_{\mu\nu}$). *The geometrization of the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic fields has been left behind by Einstein [17] himself as an unsolved problem. Besides of the many trials to extend the geometry of general relativity even to the electromagnetic field, the conceptual differences between the geometrized gravitational field and the classical Maxwellian theory of the electromagnetic field were so far insurmountable.*

Claim.

In general, the completely geometrical form of the stress-energy momentum tensor of the electromagnetic field $b_{\mu\nu}$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
b_{\mu\nu} &\equiv \frac{1}{4 \times \pi \times 4 \times D} \times ((4 \times (F_{\mu c} \times F^{\mu c})) + (D \times (F_I))) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv b \times g_{\mu\nu}
\end{aligned} \tag{180}$$

Proof by modus ponens. **If** the premise

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{(Premise)} \tag{181}$$

is true, **then** the conclusion

$$\begin{aligned} b_{\mu\nu} &\equiv \frac{1}{4 \times \pi \times 4 \times D} \times ((4 \times (F_{\mu c} \times F^{\mu c})) + (D \times (F_1))) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv b \times g_{\mu\nu} \end{aligned} \quad (182)$$

is also true, the absence of any technical errors presupposed. The premise

$$(+1) = (+1) \quad (183)$$

is true. Multiplying this premise by the stress-energy momentum tensor of the electromagnetic field $b_{\mu\nu}$, we obtain

$$(+1) \times b_{\mu\nu} \equiv (+1) \times b_{\mu\nu} \quad (184)$$

or

$$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv b_{\mu\nu} \quad (185)$$

The tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$ denotes the trace-less, symmetric stress-energy tensor of the (source-free) electromagnetic field and is defined in cgs-Gaussian units (**depending upon metric signature**) as

$$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{1}{4 \times \pi} \times \left((F_{\mu c} \times F_{\nu}^c) + \left(\frac{1}{4} \times g_{\mu\nu} \times F_{de} \times F^{de} \right) \right) \right) \quad (186)$$

[see 38, p. 13] or as

$$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{1}{4 \times \pi} \times \left((F_{\mu c} \times F_{\nu d} \times g^{cd}) - \left(\frac{1}{4} \times g_{\mu\nu} \times F_{de} \times F^{de} \right) \right) \right) \quad (187)$$

[see 33, p. 38]. A completely geometrized, co-variant stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field expressed under conditions of $D = 4$ space-time dimensions has already been published

[theorem 3.1, equation 80 8, p. 157]. Rearranging equation 185 in connection with equation 186 and according to the definition 2.32 it is

$$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{1}{4 \times \pi} \times \left(\left(F_{\mu c} \times F_{\nu d} \times g^{cd} \right) + \left(\frac{1}{4} \times g_{\mu\nu} \times F_{de} \times F^{de} \right) \right) \right) \quad (188)$$

Rearranging equation before again it is

$$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{1}{4 \times \pi} \times \left(\left(\frac{4 \times D}{4 \times D} \times \left(F_{\mu c} \times F_{\nu d} \times g^{cd} \right) \right) + \left(\left(\frac{D}{4 \times D} \times F_{de} \times F^{de} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) \quad (189)$$

where D denotes the number of space-time dimensions (see definition 2.5, equation 21).

Rearranging the equation 189 further, we obtain

$$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{1}{4 \times \pi \times 4 \times D} \times \left(\left(4 \times D \times \left(F_{\mu c} \times F_{\nu d} \times g^{cd} \right) \right) + \left(D \times \left(F_{de} \times F^{de} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) \quad (190)$$

Under conditions where $g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} \equiv D$ (see definition 2.5, equation 21) equation 190 simplifies as

$$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{1}{4 \times \pi \times 4 \times D} \times \left(\left(4 \times (g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu}) \times \left(F_{\mu c} \times F_{\nu d} \times g^{cd} \right) \right) + \left(D \times \left(F_{de} \times F^{de} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) \quad (191)$$

or as

$$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{1}{4 \times \pi \times 4 \times D} \times \left(\left(4 \times (g^{\mu\nu}) \times \left(F_{\mu c} \times F_{\nu d} \times g^{cd} \right) \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) + \left(D \times \left(F_{de} \times F^{de} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \quad (192)$$

A further simplification of the relationship before (equation 192) yields the stress-energy

momentum tensor of the electromagnetic field $b_{\mu\nu}$ determined only by the metric tensor of general relativity $g_{\mu\nu}$ as

$$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{1}{4 \times \pi \times 4 \times D} \times \left(\left(4 \times \left(F_{\mu c} \times g^{\mu\nu} \times g^{cd} \times F_{\nu d} \right) \right) + \left(D \times \left(F_{de} \times F^{de} \right) \right) \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (193)$$

However, the term $\left(\left(F_{\mu c} \times g^{\mu\nu} \times g^{cd} \times F_{\nu d} \right) + \left(F_{de} \times F^{de} \right) \right)$ of the equation 193 can be simplified further. For the first, it is $(F_1 \equiv F_{de} \times F^{de})$ (see definition 2.30, equation 55). Furthermore, for an order-2 tensor, twice multiplying by the contra-variant metric tensor and contracting [see 17, p. 790] in different indices [see 35] raises each index. In other words, according to Einstein [see 17, p. 790], it is in general $F^{\left(\begin{smallmatrix} 1 & 3 \\ \mu & c \end{smallmatrix} \right)} \equiv g^{\left(\begin{smallmatrix} 1 & 2 \\ \mu & \nu \end{smallmatrix} \right)} \times g^{\left(\begin{smallmatrix} 3 & 4 \\ c & d \end{smallmatrix} \right)} \times F_{\left(\begin{smallmatrix} \nu & d \\ 2 & 4 \end{smallmatrix} \right)}$ or more professionally $F^{\mu c} \equiv g^{\mu\nu} \times g^{cd} \times F_{\nu d}$ (see definition 2.7, equation 30) which simplifies equation 193 as

$$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{1}{4 \times \pi \times 4 \times D} \times \left(\left(4 \times \left(F_{\mu c} \times F^{\mu c} \right) \right) - \left(D \times \left(F_1 \right) \right) \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (194)$$

Equation 194 can be simplified further. Under conditions where

$$\left(F_{\mu c} \times F^{\mu c} \right) \equiv \left(F_{de} \times F^{de} \right) \equiv F_1 \quad (195)$$

and equation 194 simplifies under conditions of D space-time dimensions as

$$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{1}{4 \times \pi} \times \left(\left(\frac{4 \times F_1}{4 \times D} \right) + \left(\frac{D \times F_1}{4 \times D} \right) \right) \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (196)$$

or as

$$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{(4 + D) \times F_1}{4 \times \pi \times 4 \times D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (197)$$

In general, we define the scalar or invariant b as

$$b \equiv \left(\frac{(4 + D) \times F_1}{4 \times \pi \times 4 \times D} \right) \quad (198)$$

The 2-index stress-energy momentum tensor of the electromagnetic field geometrized completely, is given by

$$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv b \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (199)$$

In other words, our conclusion is true.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Remark 3.8. *Under the circumstances above ($F_1 \equiv F_{de} \times F^{de}$) (see definition 2.30, equation 55), the stress energy tensor of ordinary matter $a_{\mu\nu}$ follows as*

$$\begin{aligned} a_{\mu\nu} &\equiv E_{\mu\nu} - b_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) - \left(\frac{(4 + D) \times F_1}{4 \times \pi \times 4 \times D} \right) \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \end{aligned} \quad (200)$$

Theorem 3.12 (The general foundation of the Einstein field equations). *Above all, it is necessary to extend the geometrization of gravitational force to non-gravitational interactions, in particular, to electromagnetism, in order to achieve something like a geometrical unified field theory. Ultimately, not all are comfortable with the geometrization of physics. Besides of all in order to describe all fundamental interactions by appropriate objects of space-time geometry, it is necessary to work out the foundations of the Einstein field equations. The D dimensional foundation of the Einstein field equation is given by*

$$\frac{R}{D} - \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) + (\Lambda) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \quad (201)$$

Proof by modus ponens. **If** the premise of modus ponens

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{(Premise)} \quad (202)$$

is true, **then** the following conclusion

$$\frac{R}{D} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) + (\Lambda) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \quad (203)$$

is also true. The premise $(+1 = +1)$ is true. Multiplying the premise $(+1 = +1)$ by Einstein's stress-energy tensor of general relativity $T_{\mu\nu}$, we obtain

$$(+1) \times \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \equiv (+1) \times \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (204)$$

or

$$\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times 4 \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (205)$$

Einstein offered **the principle of general covariance** as the foundation of the theory of general relativity and published the relationship between curvature and momentum in the form of his field equations as $R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}$ (see definition 2.41, equation 68). Equation 205 changes too

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (206)$$

Taking the trace with respect to the metric of both sides of the Einstein field equations one gets

$$R_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} \quad (207)$$

Equation 207 simplifies as

$$R - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times D \right) + (\Lambda \times D) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T \quad (208)$$

where D is the number of space time dimensions (see definition 2.5, equation 21). Dividing equation 208 by D, the number of space-time dimensions, simplifies equation 208 further. Thus far, from the epistemological standpoint, the generally valid D dimensional foundation of the Einstein field equations is given by

$$\frac{R}{D} - \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) + (\Lambda) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \quad (209)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Theorem 3.13 (The 2-index D dimensional Einstein field equations completely geometrized). *Both admirers and sceptics agree that Einstein field equations are not completely geometrized. However, a complete geometrization of Einstein field equations may go hand-in-hand with a unification of all known interactions. Therefore, we derive now a completely geometrical form of the 2-index Einstein field equations [17, 23, 21], the mathematical foundation of the generalised theory of gravitation[24] under conditions of D dimensions [41]. The completely geometrized 2-index D dimensional Einstein field equations are given by the equation*

$$\left(\frac{R}{D} \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (210)$$

Proof by modus ponens. **If** the premise of modus ponens

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{(Premise)} \quad (211)$$

is true, **then** the following conclusion

$$\left(\frac{R}{D} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (212)$$

is also true. The premise (+1 = +1) is true. A further manipulation of the premise (+1 = +1) yields the result (see theorem 3.12, equation 209)

$$\frac{R}{D} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) + (\Lambda) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \quad (213)$$

Multiplying equation 213 by the 2-index metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ yields the 2-index D dimensional Einstein field equations as

$$\left(\frac{R}{D} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (214)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Remark 3.9. *In point of fact, due to theorem 3.3, equation 123, it is $\left(X \equiv S \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D}\right)\right)$.*

Equation 213 has been derived as

$$\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) + (\Lambda) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \quad (215)$$

According to theorem 3.7, equation 155, it is $E \equiv \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right)$ and equation 215 changes to

$$\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) + (\Lambda) \equiv E \quad (216)$$

The 2-index general geometrical form of Einstein field equation under conditions of D dimensions

is obtained by multiplying equation 216 by the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ as

$$\left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv E \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (217)$$

Einstein's general theory of relativity gave a very big boost to physics. However, there are still many and deepest problems in modern physics that remain to be solved. How does space-time develop as such? Does space-time develop from lower and more simple to higher and more complex space-time dimensions? How will space-time develop in the future? Meanwhile, various other theories entered the 'scientific market'. It is known that in M-theory [see 58, p. 1129] space-time is 11-dimensional, while in super-string theory [30] it is 10-dimensional, and in bosonic string theory [30], it is 26-dimensional. The general geometrical form of Einstein field equation under conditions of D dimensions is obtained as $\left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv E \times g_{\mu\nu}$ and should be able to cope with these theoretical challenges. However, one starting point of string theory is the idea that the point-like particles of particle physics can also be described as one-dimensional objects called strings. Under conditions of one-dimension, Einsteins field equation becomes $(R \times g_{\mu\nu}) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T \times g_{\mu\nu}$. String theory as an area of current research in theoretical physics seeks to unite the current theory of very small objects (quantum mechanics) with the theory of very large objects (general relativity). Under conditions of one-dimension, it should be possible to study the nature of strings completely by the equation $\left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T \times g_{\mu\nu}$.

Theorem 3.14 (Einstein's field equations under conditions of $D=2$ space-time dimensions).
The Einstein field equations [17, 23, 21, 24] simplifies under conditions of two space-time dimensions as

$$(\Lambda) \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{4 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (218)$$

Proof by modus ponens. **If** the premise of modus ponens

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{(Premise)} \quad (219)$$

is true, **then** the following conclusion

$$(\Lambda) \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{4 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (220)$$

is also true, again the absence of any technical errors presupposed. The premise

$$+ 1 \equiv +1 \quad (221)$$

is true. Multiplying this premise by Einstein's stress-energy tensor of general relativity, we obtain

$$+ 1 \times \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times \left(\frac{T}{D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv +1 \times \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times \left(\frac{T}{D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (222)$$

or

$$\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times \left(\frac{T}{D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times \left(\frac{T}{D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (223)$$

According to Einstein it is $R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu}$ (see definition 2.41). In connection with theorem 3.12, equation 209 (see theorem 3.12, equation 209), equation 223 changes to

$$\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times \left(\frac{T}{D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (224)$$

which is the general form of the 2-index Einstein's field equations under conditions of D dimensions. Under conditions of D=2 space-time conditions, the 2-index Einstein's field

equations becomes

$$\left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times \left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (225)$$

or

$$0 + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times \left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (226)$$

To bring it again to the point. under conditions of D dimensions it is

$$(\Lambda) \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{4 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (227)$$

In other words, our conclusion is true.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Remark 3.10. Under conditions of $D=2$ space-time dimensions equation 227 determines Einstein's cosmological constant as $\Lambda \equiv \left(\frac{4 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T$ or something as $\Lambda \approx T$.

Theorem 3.15 (The 4-index D dimensional Einstein field equations completely geometrized).

The 4-index D dimensional Einstein field equations completely geometrized are given by

$$\left(\frac{R}{D} \times g_{kl\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{kl\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \quad (228)$$

Proof by modus ponens. **If** the premise of modus ponens

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{(Premise)} \quad (229)$$

is true, **then** the following conclusion

$$\left(\frac{R}{D} \times g_{kl\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{kl\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \quad (230)$$

is also true. The premise (+1 = +1) is true. A further manipulation of the premise (+1 = +1) yields the result (see theorem 3.12, equation 209)

$$\frac{R}{D} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) + (\Lambda) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \quad (231)$$

Multiplying equation 231 by the 4-index metric tensor $g_{kl\mu\nu}$ yields the 4-index D dimensional Einstein field equations completely geometrized as

$$\left(\frac{R}{D} \times g_{kl\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{kl\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \quad (232)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Remark 3.11. *The 4-index D dimensional Einstein field equations can be simplified more or less as $G_{kl\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu}$. As already pointed out, it is possible to split the Riemannian tensor $R_{kl\mu\nu}$ into different ways, including the Weyl conformal tensor [56], denoted by $C_{kl\mu\nu}$, and the anti-Weyl conformal tensor $\underline{C}_{kl\mu\nu}$. The anti-Weyl conformal tensor denoted as $\underline{C}_{kl\mu\nu}$ is the part of the Riemannian tensor $R_{kl\mu\nu}$ which involves the Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ and the curvature scalar R . In general, it is $(R_{kl\mu\nu} \equiv C_{kl\mu\nu} + \underline{C}_{kl\mu\nu})$ (see definition 2.21). Under these circumstances, the 4-index D dimensional Einstein field equations becomes $C_{kl\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{kl\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu}) + \underline{C}_{kl\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu}$.*

Theorem 3.16 (The n-index D dimensional Einstein field equations completely geometrized).

The n -index D dimensional Einstein field equations completely geometrized are given by

$$\left(\frac{R}{D} \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \quad (233)$$

Proof by modus ponens. **If** the premise of modus ponens

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{(Premise)} \quad (234)$$

is true, **then** the following conclusion

$$\left(\frac{R}{D} \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \quad (235)$$

is also true. The premise $(+1 = +1)$ is true. A further manipulation of the premise $(+1 = +1)$ yields the result (see theorem 3.12, equation 209)

$$\frac{R}{D} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) + (\Lambda) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \quad (236)$$

Multiplying equation 236 by the n -index metric tensor $g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots$ yields the n -index D dimensional Einstein field equations completely geometrized as

$$\left(\frac{R}{D} \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \dots \quad (237)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Theorem 3.17 (Einstein's cosmological constant Λ). *On the whole, the level of uncertainty [31, 14] among the scientist and especially physicist is high despite the growing evidence [4, 3, 7, 2, 13, 5, 1] to the contrary already available. An even more severe violation of our trust*

into physics is created by the cosmological constant Λ too, which is taken to specify the overall vacuum energy density. Depending on the specific assumptions made, the physical value [54] of the cosmological constant Λ is found to be very contradictory. The value of the cosmological constant Λ depends on the number of space-time dimensions D too. In general, the value of the cosmological constant Λ is given by

$$\Lambda \equiv \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times \frac{T}{D} \right) + \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \quad (238)$$

Proof by modus ponens. **If** the premise of modus ponens

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{(Premise)} \quad (239)$$

is true, **then** the following conclusion

$$\Lambda \equiv \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times \frac{T}{D} \right) + \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \quad (240)$$

is also true, again the absence of any technical errors presupposed. The premise

$$+ 1 \equiv +1 \quad (241)$$

is true. Multiplying this premise by Einstein's stress-energy tensor of general relativity, we obtain

$$(+1) \times \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \equiv (+1) \times \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (242)$$

or

$$\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times 4 \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (243)$$

According to Einstein (definition 2.41), equation 243 changes to

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (244)$$

Taking the trace with respect to the metric of both sides of the Einstein field equations one gets

$$R_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} \quad (245)$$

According to definition 2.5 (definition 2.5, equation 21), equation 245 simplifies as

$$R - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times D \right) + (\Lambda \times D) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T \quad (246)$$

Dividing equation 246 by D, the number of space-time dimensions, it is

$$\frac{R}{D} - \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) + (\Lambda) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \quad (247)$$

Rearranging equation 247 yields **the exact value of Einstein's cosmological constant Λ in relation to space-time dimensions D** as

$$\Lambda \equiv \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times \frac{T}{D} \right) + \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \quad (248)$$

In other words, our conclusion is true.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Remark 3.12. *One important outcome of theorem 3.17, equation 248 is the discovery that the exact value of Einstein's cosmological constant Λ depends on D, the number of space-time dimensions and probably vice versa. It is evident to all of us that theorem 3.17, equation 248 provides crystal clear and objectively provable facts that Einstein's cosmological*

constant Λ cannot be treated as a constant. Additionally, especially appropriate measurements and experiments may prove as true that theorem 3.17 induces more than only reasonable doubts with respect to the constancy of Einstein's cosmological constant Λ . Furthermore, one striking consequence of theorem 3.17, equation 248 is the fact that as soon as Λ is known, it is possible to calculate the number of space-time dimensions D of a manifold (theorem 3.17, equation 248).

Theorem 3.18 (Anti cosmological constant $\underline{\Lambda}$). *The value of the anti-cosmological constant $\underline{\Lambda}$ can be calculated very precisely. In general, the value of the anti-cosmological constant $\underline{\Lambda}$ [17, 23, 21] is given by*

$$\underline{\Lambda} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) + \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times \frac{T}{D}\right) \quad (249)$$

Proof by modus ponens. **If** the premise of modus ponens

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{(Premise)} \quad (250)$$

is true, **then** the following conclusion

$$\underline{\Lambda} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) + \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times \frac{T}{D}\right) \quad (251)$$

is also true, again the absence of any technical errors presupposed. The premise

$$+ 1 \equiv +1 \quad (252)$$

is true. Multiplying this premise by Ricci scalar (see definition 2.8), we obtain

$$(+1) \times (R) \equiv (+1) \times (R) \quad (253)$$

or

$$R \equiv R \quad (254)$$

Adding Λ and subtracting Λ , the cosmological constant, it is

$$R - \Lambda + \Lambda \equiv R - \Lambda + \Lambda \quad (255)$$

or

$$R - \Lambda + \Lambda \equiv R + 0 \quad (256)$$

According to our definition 2.8 it is

$$\underline{\Lambda} + \Lambda \equiv R \quad (257)$$

and therefore

$$\underline{\Lambda} \equiv R - \Lambda \quad (258)$$

The exact value of the cosmological constant Λ under conditions of D space-time dimensions was calculated by theorem 3.17, equation 248 as $\Lambda \equiv \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times \frac{T}{D} \right) + \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - \left(\frac{R}{D} \right)$.

The exact value of the anti cosmological constant $\underline{\Lambda}$ can be calculated as

$$\underline{\Lambda} \equiv R - \left(\left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times \frac{T}{D} \right) + \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \right) \quad (259)$$

or as

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{\Lambda} &\equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) + \left(\frac{2 \times R}{2} \right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) + \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times \frac{T}{D} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (260)$$

with the consequence that our conclusion is true.

Quod erat demonstrandum.

4. Discussion

Having overthrown the Newtonian gravitational theory, the general theory of relativity did not enable general relativity's geometrization of gravitation to non-gravitational interactions, in particular, to electromagnetism. Among Weyl and Eddington and other, Einstein was one of the first to use explicitly the term “**unified field theory**” in the title [18] of a publication in 1925. In the following, Einstein himself published more than thirty technical papers on unification of all physical interactions. However, Einstein's unified field theory program was in vain [12, 11]. Further lack of clarity to geometrize all fundamental interactions and to provide a completely geometrized [24] theory of relativity stemmed from the cosmological constant Λ , the energy density of space, or vacuum energy, and the uncertainties associated with the same. Although some physicists including Einstein himself initially opposed the cosmological constant Λ , today, there is some experimental evidence (Perlmutter et al. [44] *Supernova Cosmology Project* and Riess et al. [48] *High-Z Supernova Search Team*) that the expansion of the universe is accelerating, implying the possibility of a positive nonzero value for the cosmological constant Λ . Considered Einstein's insight [see 17, p. 796] that $g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} \equiv D = +4$ (definition 2.5) it was possible to geometrize the Einstein field equations under conditions of D dimensions. The 2-index Einstein field equations under conditions of D dimensions (see theorem 3.13, equation 214) might be seen as fully compliant with the relationship

$$\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times \left(\frac{T}{D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$$

Encouraged by this result, it was possible to calculate **the exact value of the cosmological constant Λ under conditions where $g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} \equiv D$** (definition 2.5). However, an answer

to the question whether the condition $g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} \equiv D$ is generally given may predominantly be found elsewhere. Under conditions where $g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} \equiv D$ where D is the number of space-time dimensions, we are able to calculate the exact value of the cosmological constant Λ very precisely as

$$\Lambda \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) + \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - \left(\frac{R}{D} \right)$$

and much more than this. For the reasons set out above, the inevitable conclusion is that even the value of the anti cosmological constant $\underline{\Lambda}$ follows as

$$\underline{\Lambda} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) + \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right).$$

5. Conclusion

In combination with other already published [12, 11] papers, Einstein's general theory of relativity is completely geometrized. The theoretical value of the cosmological constant Λ and the value of the anti cosmological constant $\underline{\Lambda}$ was calculated very precisely.

Appendix

None.

References

- [1] Ilija Barukčić. "Anti Bohr — Quantum Theory and Causality". In: *International Journal of Applied Physics and Mathematics* 7.2 (2017), pp. 93–111. DOI: 10.17706/ijapm.2017.7.2.93–111.
- [2] Ilija Barukčić. "Anti Chsh—Refutation of the Chsh Inequality". In: *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics* 04.04 (2016), pp. 686–696. ISSN: 2327-4352. DOI: 10.4236/jamp.2016.44079.

- [3] Ilija Barukčić. “Anti Einstein – Refutation of Einstein’s General Theory of Relativity”. In: *International Journal of Applied Physics and Mathematics* 5.1 (2015), pp. 18–28. DOI: 10.17706/ijapm.2015.5.1.18-28.
- [4] Ilija Barukčić. “Anti Heisenberg-Refutation Of Heisenberg’s Uncertainty Relation”. In: *American Institute of Physics - Conference Proceedings*. Vol. 1327. Växjö, (Sweden), Jan. 2011, pp. 322–325. DOI: 10.1063/1.3567453. URL: <https://aip.scitation.org/doi/abs/10.1063/1.3567453>.
- [5] Ilija Barukčić. “Anti Heisenberg—The End of Heisenberg’s Uncertainty Principle”. In: *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics* 04.05 (2016), pp. 881–887. ISSN: 2327-4352. DOI: 10.4236/jamp.2016.45096.
- [6] Ilija Barukčić. “Anti Newton - Refutation Of The Constancy Of Newton’s Gravitational Constant G: List of Abstracts”. In: *Quantum Theory: from Problems to Advances (QTPA 2014) : Växjö, Sweden, June 9-12, 2014* (Jan. 2014), p. 63.
- [7] Ilija Barukčić. “Anti Newton — Refutation of the Constancy of Newton’s Gravitational Constant Big G”. In: *International Journal of Applied Physics and Mathematics* 5.2 (2015), pp. 126–136. DOI: 10.17706/ijapm.2015.5.2.126-136.
- [8] Ilija Barukčić. “Einstein’s field equations and non-locality”. English. In: *International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology IJMTT* 66.6 (2020). Publisher: Seventh Sense Research Group SSRG, pp. 146–167. DOI: 10.14445/22315373/IJMTT-V66I6P515. URL: <http://www.ijmttjournal.org/archive/ijmtt-v66i6p515> (visited on 06/25/2020).
- [9] Ilija Barukčić. “Newton’s Gravitational Constant Big G Is Not a Constant”. In: *Journal of Modern Physics* 07.06 (2016), pp. 510–522. ISSN: 2153-1196. DOI: 10.4236/jmp.2016.76053.

- [10] Ilija Barukčić. “The Equivalence of Time and Gravitational Field”. In: *Physics Procedia* 22 (Jan. 2011), pp. 56–62. ISSN: 18753892. DOI: 10.1016/j.phpro.2011.11.008.
- [11] Ilija Barukčić. “The Geometrization of the Electromagnetic Field”. In: *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics* 04.12 (2016), pp. 2135–2171. ISSN: 2327-4352. DOI: 10.4236/jamp.2016.412211.
- [12] Ilija Barukčić. “Unified Field Theory”. en. In: *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics* 04.08 (Aug. 2016), pp. 1379–1438. DOI: 10.4236/jamp.2016.48147. URL: <https://www.scirp.org/journal/PaperInformation.aspx?PaperID=69478&#abstract> (visited on 01/12/2019).
- [13] Jan Pavo Barukčić and Ilija Barukčić. “Anti Aristotle—The Division of Zero by Zero”. In: *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics* 04.04 (Jan. 2016), pp. 749–761. ISSN: 2327-4352. DOI: 10.4236/jamp.2016.44085.
- [14] John Stewart Bell. “On the Einstein Podolsky Rosen paradox”. en. In: *Physics* 1.3 (Nov. 1964), pp. 195–200. ISSN: 0554-128X. DOI: 10.1103/PhysicsPhysiqueFizika.1.195. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysicsPhysiqueFizika.1.195> (visited on 02/12/2019).
- [15] F. W. Dyson, A. S. Eddington, and C. Davidson. “A Determination of the Deflection of Light by the Sun’s Gravitational Field, from Observations Made at the Total Eclipse of May 29, 1919”. In: *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Containing Papers of a Mathematical or Physical Character* 220 (1920). Publisher: The Royal Society, pp. 291–333. ISSN: 0264-3952. DOI: 10.2307/91137. URL: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/91137> (visited on 09/01/2020).
- [16] Kenny Easwaran. “The Role of Axioms in Mathematics”. en. In: *Erkenntnis* 68.3 (May 2008), pp. 381–391. ISSN: 1572-8420. DOI: 10.1007/s10670-008-9106-1. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10670-008-9106-1> (visited on 12/08/2019).

- [17] A. Einstein. “Die Grundlage der allgemeinen Relativitätstheorie”. In: *Annalen der Physik* 354 (1916), pp. 769–822. ISSN: 0003-3804. DOI: 10.1002/andp.19163540702. URL: <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1916AnP...354..769E> (visited on 03/07/2019).
- [18] A. Einstein. “Einheitliche Feldtheorie von Gravitation und Elektrizität”. en. In: *Preussische Akademie der Wissenschaften, Phys.-math. Klasse, Sitzungsberichte* (1925), pp. 414–419. DOI: 10.1002/3527608958.ch30. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/3527608958.ch30> (visited on 05/16/2020).
- [19] A. Einstein. “Elementary Derivation of the Equivalence of Mass and Energy”. en. In: *Bulletin of the American Mathematical Society* 41.4 (1935), pp. 223–230. URL: https://projecteuclid.org/download/pdf_1/euclid.bams/1183498131.
- [20] A. Einstein. “Zur Elektrodynamik bewegter Körper”. en. In: *Annalen der Physik* 322.10 (1905), pp. 891–921. ISSN: 1521-3889. DOI: 10.1002/andp.19053221004. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/andp.19053221004> (visited on 02/12/2019).
- [21] A. Einstein and W. de Sitter. “On the Relation between the Expansion and the Mean Density of the Universe”. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 18.3 (Mar. 1932), pp. 213–214. ISSN: 0027-8424. URL: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1076193/> (visited on 02/12/2019).
- [22] Albert Einstein. “Die Feldgleichungen der Gravitation”. In: *Sitzungsberichte der Königlich Preußischen Akademie der Wissenschaften (Berlin)*, Seite 844-847. (1915). URL: <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1915SPAW.....844E> (visited on 02/12/2019).
- [23] Albert Einstein. “Kosmologische Betrachtungen zur allgemeinen Relativitätstheorie”. In: *Sitzungsberichte der Königlich Preußischen Akademie der Wissenschaften (Berlin)*, Seite 142-152. (1917). URL: <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1917SPAW.....142E> (visited on 02/12/2019).

- [24] Albert Einstein. “On the Generalized Theory of Gravitation”. In: *Scientific American* 182 (Apr. 1950), pp. 13–17. ISSN: 0036-8733. DOI: 10.1038/scientificamerican0450-13. URL: <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1950SciAm.182d..13E> (visited on 02/12/2019).
- [25] Albert Einstein. *The meaning of relativity. Four lectures delivered at Princeton University, May, 1921*. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1923. (Visited on 03/07/2019).
- [26] Albert Einstein and Marcel Grossmann. *Entwurf einer verallgemeinerten Relativitätstheorie und einer Theorie der Gravitation: Physikalischer Teil von Albert Einstein. Mathematischer Teil von Marcel Grossmann*. Leipzig: B. G. Teubner, 1913.
- [27] C. A. Escobar and L. F. Urrutia. “Invariants of the electromagnetic field”. In: *Journal of Mathematical Physics* 55.3 (Mar. 2014). Publisher: American Institute of Physics, p. 032902. ISSN: 0022-2488. DOI: 10.1063/1.4868478. URL: <https://aip.scitation.org/doi/10.1063/1.4868478> (visited on 09/10/2020).
- [28] Paul Finsler. “Über Kurven und Flächen in allgemeinen Räumen”. German. PhD thesis. Göttingen: Georg-August Universität, 1918. URL: <https://gdz.sub.uni-g%7B%5C%22o%7Dttingen.de/id/PPN321583582>.
- [29] Hubert F. M. Goenner. “On the History of Unified Field Theories”. In: *Living Reviews in Relativity* 7.1 (2004). ISSN: 1433-8351. DOI: 10.12942/lrr-2004-2. URL: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5256024/> (visited on 12/18/2019).
- [30] Sebastian de Haro et al. “Forty Years of String Theory Reflecting on the Foundations”. en. In: *Foundations of Physics* 43.1 (Jan. 2013), pp. 1–7. ISSN: 1572-9516. DOI: 10.1007/s10701-012-9691-3. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10701-012-9691-3> (visited on 07/29/2020).
- [31] W. Heisenberg. “Über den anschaulichen Inhalt der quantentheoretischen Kinematik und Mechanik”. de. In: *Zeitschrift für Physik* 43.3 (Mar. 1927), pp. 172–198. ISSN: 0044-3328.

- DOI: 10.1007/BF01397280. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01397280> (visited on 02/12/2019).
- [32] David Hilbert. “Axiomatisches Denken”. de. In: *Mathematische Annalen* 78.1 (Dec. 1917), pp. 405–415. ISSN: 1432-1807. DOI: 10.1007/BF01457115. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01457115> (visited on 05/30/2019).
- [33] L. P. Hughston and K. P. Tod. *An introduction to general relativity*. London Mathematical Society student texts 5. Cambridge ; New York: Cambridge University Press, 1990. ISBN: 978-0-521-32705-3.
- [34] Theodor Kaluza. “Zum Unitätsproblem der Physik”. ger. In: *Sitzungsberichte der Königlich Preußischen Akademie der Wissenschaften* (1921). Journal Abbreviation: *Sitzungsber. Königl. Preuss. Akad. Wiss.*, pp. 966–972.
- [35] David C. Kay. *Schaum’s outline of theory and problems of tensor calculus*. Schaum’s outline series. Schaum’s outline series in mathematics. New York: McGraw-Hill, 1988. ISBN: 978-0-07-033484-7.
- [36] Leopold Kronecker. “Ueber bilineare Formen”. In: *Journal für die reine und angewandte Mathematik (Crelle’s Journal)* 68 (1868), pp. 273–285.
- [37] M. Laue. “Zur Dynamik der Relativitätstheorie”. en. In: *Annalen der Physik* 340.8 (1911), pp. 524–542. ISSN: 1521-3889. DOI: 10.1002/andp.19113400808. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/andp.19113400808> (visited on 05/16/2020).
- [38] D. Lehmkuhl. “Mass-Energy-Momentum: Only there Because of Spacetime?” en. In: *The British Journal for the Philosophy of Science* 62.3 (Sept. 2011), pp. 453–488. ISSN: 0007-0882, 1464-3537. DOI: 10.1093/bjps/axr003. URL: <https://academic.oup.com/bjps/article-lookup/doi/10.1093/bjps/axr003> (visited on 05/16/2020).

- [39] Dennis Lehmkuhl. “Why Einstein did not believe that general relativity geometrizes gravity”. In: *Studies in History and Philosophy of Science Part B: Studies in History and Philosophy of Modern Physics* 46 (May 2014), pp. 316–326. ISSN: 1355-2198. DOI: 10.1016/j.shpsb.2013.08.002. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1355219813000695> (visited on 07/14/2019).
- [40] Tomáš Málek. “General Relativity in Higher Dimensions”. Englisch. PhD thesis. Prague: Institute of Theoretical Physics. Faculty of Mathematics and Physics. Charles University, 2012. URL: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1204.0291.pdf>.
- [41] Frédéric Moulin. “Generalization of Einstein’s gravitational field equations”. en. In: *The European Physical Journal C* 77.12 (Dec. 2017), p. 878. ISSN: 1434-6052. DOI: 10.1140/epjc/s10052-017-5452-y. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjc/s10052-017-5452-y> (visited on 07/31/2020).
- [42] Isaac Newton. *Philosophiae naturalis principia mathematica*. lat. Londini: Jussu Societatis Regiae ac Typis Josephi Streater. Prostat apud plures bibliopolas, 1687. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5479/sil.52126.39088015628399> (visited on 02/12/2019).
- [43] Gunnar Nordström. “Über die Möglichkeit, das elektromagnetische Feld und das Gravitationsfeld zu vereinigen”. In: *Physikalische Zeitschrift* 15 (1914), pp. 504–506. URL: <http://publikationen.ub.uni-frankfurt.de/frontdoor/index/index/docId/17520>.
- [44] S. Perlmutter et al. “Measurements of Omega and Lamda from 42 High-Redshift Supernovae”. en. In: *The Astrophysical Journal* 517.2 (June 1999). Publisher: IOP Publishing, p. 565. ISSN: 0004-637X. DOI: 10.1086/307221. URL: <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1086/307221/meta> (visited on 05/16/2020).
- [45] M. M. G. Ricci and T. Levi-Civita. “Méthodes de calcul différentiel absolu et leurs applications”. fr. In: *Mathematische Annalen* 54.1 (Mar. 1900), pp. 125–201. ISSN: 1432-

1807. DOI: 10.1007/BF01454201. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01454201> (visited on 05/13/2020).
- [46] Georg Friedrich Bernhard Riemann. “Über die Hypothesen, welche der Geometrie zu Grunde liegen”. PhD thesis. Göttingen: Universität Göttingen, 1854.
- [47] Georg Friedrich Bernhard Riemann. “Über die Hypothesen, welche der Geometrie zu Grunde liegen”. de. In: *Physikalische Blätter* 10.7 (1954). Reprint, pp. 296–306. ISSN: 1521-3722. DOI: 10.1002/phbl.19540100702. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/phbl.19540100702> (visited on 09/12/2020).
- [48] Adam G. Riess et al. “Observational Evidence from Supernovae for an Accelerating Universe and a Cosmological Constant”. en. In: *The Astronomical Journal* 116.3 (Sept. 1998). Publisher: IOP Publishing, p. 1009. ISSN: 1538-3881. DOI: 10.1086/300499. URL: <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1086/300499/meta> (visited on 05/16/2020).
- [49] Willem de Sitter. “On the curvature of space”. In: *Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen Proceedings Series B Physical Sciences* 20 (1917), pp. 229–243. URL: <https://www.dwc.knaw.nl/DL/publications/PU00012216.pdf> (visited on 08/30/2020).
- [50] Willem de Sitter. “On the relativity of inertia. Remarks concerning Einstein’s latest hypothesis”. In: *Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen Proceedings Series B Physical Sciences* 19 (Mar. 1917), pp. 1217–1225. URL: <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1917KNAB...19.1217D> (visited on 08/30/2020).
- [51] Hans Stephani, ed. *Exact solutions of Einstein’s field equations*. 2nd ed. Cambridge monographs on mathematical physics. Cambridge, UK ; New York: Cambridge University Press, 2003. ISBN: 978-0-521-46136-8.
- [52] Joseph Thmoson. “Joint eclipse meeting of the Royal Society and the Royal Astronomical Society”. In: *The Observatory* 42.545 (1919), pp. 89–398. URL: <http://articles.adsabs.>

harvard.edu/cgi-bin/t2png?bg=%23FFFFFF&/seri/Obs../0042/600/0000389.000&
db_key=AST&bits=4&res=100&filetype=.gif.

- [53] G. Vranceanu. “Sur une théorie unitaire non holonome des champs physiques”. In: *Journal de Physique et le Radium* 7.12 (1936), pp. 514–526. ISSN: 0368-3842. DOI: 10.1051/jphysrad:01936007012051400. URL: <http://www.edpsciences.org/10.1051/jphysrad:01936007012051400> (visited on 02/12/2019).
- [54] Steven Weinberg. “Anthropic Bound on the Cosmological Constant”. In: *Physical Review Letters* 59.22 (Nov. 1987). Publisher: American Physical Society, pp. 2607–2610. DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevLett.59.2607. URL: <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.59.2607> (visited on 05/17/2020).
- [55] Hermann Weyl. “Gravitation und Elektrizität”. In: *Sitzungsberichte der Königlich Preußischen Akademie der Wissenschaften* (1918), pp. 465–478.
- [56] Hermann Weyl. “Reine Infinitesimalgeometrie”. de. In: *Mathematische Zeitschrift* 2.3 (Sept. 1918), pp. 384–411. ISSN: 1432-1823. DOI: 10.1007/BF01199420. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01199420> (visited on 06/12/2020).
- [57] Andrew Wiles. “Modular Elliptic Curves and Fermat’s Last Theorem”. In: *Annals of Mathematics* 141.3 (1995). Publisher: Annals of Mathematics, pp. 443–551. ISSN: 0003-486X. DOI: 10.2307/2118559. URL: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2118559> (visited on 09/27/2020).
- [58] Edward Witten. “Magic, Mystery, and Matrix”. In: *Notices of the American Mathematical Society* 45.9 (1998), pp. 1124–1129. URL: [https://www.sns.ias.edu/sites/default/files/mmm\(3\).pdf](https://www.sns.ias.edu/sites/default/files/mmm(3).pdf).
- [59] Edward Witten. “String theory dynamics in various dimensions”. en. In: *Nuclear Physics B* 443.1 (June 1995), pp. 85–126. ISSN: 0550-3213. DOI: 10.1016/0550-3213(95)00158-0.

URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0550321395001580>

(visited on 09/03/2020).

- [60] Shwu Yeng, T. Lin, and You-Feng Lin. “The n-dimensional pythagorean theorem”. en. In: *Linear and Multilinear Algebra* (Apr. 2008). Publisher: Gordon and Breach Science Publishers. DOI: 10.1080/03081089008817961. URL: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/03081089008817961> (visited on 09/09/2020).
- [61] G Zehfuss. “Über eine gewisse Determinante”. In: *Zeitschrift für Mathematik und Physik* 3 (1858), pp. 298–301.